

ETHICAL AND LEGAL GUIDELINES FOR RESEARCH DATA MANAGEMENT: THE CIRCE EXPERIENCE AS A TRANSFERABLE MODEL

Silvia Calamai, Claudia Soria, Chiara Silvia
Angiolini, Philipp Meer, Robert Fuchs,
Luís Guerra, Lili Cavalheiro, Amna
Brdarević-Čeljo, Vildana Dubravac

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Rationale of the Guidelines

The CIRCE (*Counteracting accent discrimination practices in education*) project (www.circe-project.eu) is a funded ERASMUS+ project (2022-1-IT02-KA220-SCH-000087602) active between 30.12.2023 and 30.12.2025). The project involved different European countries (Italy, Portugal, Germany) and an associated country in Europe (Bosnia Herzegovina) and included extensive fieldwork both in secondary school and university settings.

Given the nature of the activities, the project necessarily involved the collection, processing, sharing, and long-term preservation of data, including personal data. This made it necessary to set up a shared framework for data management, compliant with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) and with its implementation in national legal systems.

This document describes the measures and the actions adopted by the project to ensure a fair, lawful, and ethically sound management of data collected and shared by the project. While grounded in the specific experience of CIRCE, the guidelines are intentionally formulated in a way that makes them **transferable** to other research project operating in comparable contexts, particularly those involving international consortia and fieldwork with school participants. Several of the measures described are mutually interdependent and in some cases recursive. The order in which they are presented in these *Guidelines* reflects the order of the issues encountered during the project. This order can be adapted to different institutional, legal, or research requirements.

All documents cited in the project are in English. Whenever it was important for a document to reach non-specialist audiences, it was translated into the relevant national languages.

1. Before collecting data

In the first months of a project, it is recommendable to write a **Data Management Plan**, including a description of the data that will be collected, the metadata and documentation that will be produced, the ways the data will be stored and backed up, security and privacy issues for sensitive data, data access policies during the project itself, and a long-term plan for data sharing and preservation.

The CIRCE Data management plan (DMP)

In the CIRCE project, the DMP was conceived as a living document, evolving alongside the project activities. Two versions were made publicly available through Zenodo (version 0, 8/11/2023 and version 1, 5/11/2024), reflecting different stages of processing in fieldwork. The DMP is accessible at <https://zenodo.org/records/10085133>

The DMP is also accessible via the CIRCE website: <https://www.circe-project.eu/circes-code-of-conduct-and-dmp/>

Making the DMP publicly accessible contributes to transparency, accountability, and the promotion of open science practices.

Internal Governance: the Project Reference Manual

In addition to publicly available documentation, the project developed a **Project Reference Manual**, intended for internal use by all partners as an operational tool supporting collaboration within the consortium. It is an

internal document helping all the members of the project in technical and management issues (e.g., workflow, organisation of the meetings, quality assessment). It is intended as an instrument to facilitate collaboration among the project partners towards the achievement of the goals of the project. It defines the roles and functions of groups and individuals, as well as the procedures to be followed in management, communication, documentation, deviation identification and correction activities. It can be shared upon request by writing to contact@circe.eu.

2. Data sharing within the consortium

Before sharing data among partners, it is essential that all collaborators have a clear understanding of the data lifecycle, and must be aware of which entity, alone or jointly with others, determines the purposes and means of the processing of personal data.

After extensive discussion, the CIRCE EU partners agreed to a regime of joint controllership for data processing activities. Joint controllership arises where two or more entities jointly participate in determining both the purposes and means of data processing. A Joint Controller Agreement was therefore established between the project coordinator and the European Union partners. The agreement defines:

- . respective responsibilities;
- . modalities of cooperation;
- . procedures for ensuring compliance with data protection obligations.

An anonymised version of the agreement is included below for reference (see Appendix 1).

2.1 Data Transfers to Partners outside the European Union

Since not all countries eligible to participate in the ERASMUS+ Programme are part of the European common area, it was also necessary to find a legal framework for sharing data with partners outside the EU.

This was the case of Bosnia and Herzegovina. We therefore asked the partner located in Bosnia and Herzegovina for a **DOCUMENT ON BOSNIAN LEGISLATION CONCERNING PERSONAL DATA PROTECTION** signed by the Legal representative of the Bosnian institution.

Standard Contractual Clauses were signed by all partners and **TECHNICAL AND ORGANISATIONAL MEASURES INCLUDING TECHNICAL AND ORGANISATIONAL MEASURES TO ENSURE THE SECURITY OF THE DATA** were provided. Additionally, a **Transfer Impact Assessment (TIA)** was provided. Anonymised versions of both documents are included below for reference (see Appendix 2-3).

The legal framework for data protection in Bosnia and Herzegovina underwent a significant transition during the lifecycle of the CIRCe project. On February 28, 2025, the new Law on Personal Data Protection was published in the Official Gazette of BiH, No. 12/25. This law, which entered into force on March 8, 2025, and became applicable on October 4, 2025, fully aligns the national legislation with the EU General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) 2016/679.

Data collection in the CIRCE project took place before October 4, 2025.

2.2 National Legal Requirements: the Italian case

In compliance with Italian data protection law and institutional regulations, additional documentation was required for projects involving personal data. In the CIRCE project, this included:

- a) a form describing the project pursuant to Article 3 of “Regole deontologiche per trattamenti a fini statistici o di ricerca scientifica dell'allegato A4 del c.d."codice privacy" (d.lgs. 196/2003)” and
 - b) a declaration of commitment signed by all the Italian project members.
- These documents are included below for reference (see Appendix n.4-5).

3. Relationship with research participants and educational institutions

Research projects involving schools, students, and other human participants require particular attention to transparency, informed consent, and accessibility of information. In CIRCE, detailed privacy policy and consent forms were provided in different versions, depending on the different types of data collected, the age of participants (minors or adults), and the specific activity involved.

A general privacy policy and consent form was translated into all the languages of the project (i.e., Italian, German, Bosnian, Portuguese) and it was mainly used for initial contact with secondary schools. More specific documents were provided for activities such as:

- . voice sample recording and collection;
- . participation in Verbal Guise Tests;
- . podcast creation;
- . interview recording;
- . collection of linguistic autobiographies.

All the documents in English are included below for reference (Appendix 6). Their Italian, German, Bosnian, Portuguese can be shared upon request by writing to contact@circe.eu.

Please note that in the English versions are written from the the Italian perspective (considering the fact that in the Project the coordinator is an Italian institution).

4. Ethical issues

Legal compliance alone is not sufficient to ensure responsible practices. Throughout the lifecycle of a project, it is equally important to adopt an approach that respects the rights, dignity, and wellbeing of all parties involved, including participants, researchers, and institutions.

4.1 Code of Conduct

The CIRCE *Code of Conduct* provides general ethical principles on how project members should operate during fieldwork, meetings and collaborative activities, publication, conferences, public events, committee and other work, mentoring relationships, and in all online spaces including (but not limited to) CIRCE social media accounts and websites. It is available in English, Bosnian, German, Italian, and Portuguese.

It provides guidance on how to act within the project, and externally, towards students and schools in general, and towards the general public. It can be download from the CIRCE website:

<https://www.circe-project.eu/circs-code-of-conduct-and-dmp/>

4.2 Ethical Review

Each partner institution in a project operates under its own ethic committee. In the CIRCE project, the coordinator requested a formal opinion from the *Ethics Committee for Research in the Human and Social Sciences - CAREUS* at the University of Siena. The committee assessed the project on the basis of an ethical-legal analysis of the proposed research activities and experimental protocols in compliance with the ethical

principles set out in the Italian Constitution, the European Charter for Researchers and the Code of Conduct for the Recruitment of Researchers, the above-mentioned international conventions, the Statute and Code of Ethics of the University Community. The committee's mandate includes:

- a. safeguarding the rights, dignity, integrity and wellbeing of individuals involved in research programmes and projects in the human and social sciences;
- b. promoting respect, protection and conservation of the environment in all its dimensions and components;
- c. guaranteeing the freedom and promotion of research in compliance with the principles above.

The CIRCE project received a positive evaluation by the CAREUS.

5. Conclusion

The measures described in this document illustrate one possible approach to managing ethical and legal challenges in international projects involving human participants and personal data.

While rooted in the specific experience of CIRCE, these guidelines are intended as a flexible framework that can be adapted to different disciplinary, institutional, and national contexts. Researchers and institutions are encouraged to reuse, modify, and build upon these practices in accordance with their own legal obligations and research needs.

Appendices

Appendix 1 – CIRCE Joint Controller Agreement (“JCA”)

With the support of the
Erasmus+ Programme
of the European Union

Joint Controller Agreement (“JCA”)

Pursuant to Article 26 of the EU Regulation 2016/679

for the Erasmus+ KA2 Cooperation Project:

**“Counteracting accent discrimination pRactiCes in Education
(CIRCE)”**

AGREEMENT NUMBER: 2022-1-IT02-KA220-SCH-000087602

PROJECT CODE: 2022-1-IT02-KA220-SCH-000087602 OID E10209118

CUP B61I22000680006

JOINT CONTROLLER AGREEMENT BETWEEN THE PROJECT COORDINATOR AND THE EU PARTNER

This Joint Controller Agreement shall govern relations between the following parties:

Università degli Studi di Siena

with headquarters in Banchi di Sotto 55, 53100 Siena – Italy

hereafter referred to as "the Joint controller",

represented by

Prof. Dr. **, Legal Representative, Rector

Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche (hereinafter: CNR)

with headquarters in Piazzale Aldo Moro 7, 00185 Roma – Italy

hereinafter referred to as to as "the Joint controller",

represented by **, Legal Representative,

Universität Hamburg

with headquarters in Mittelweg 177 20148 Hamburg – Germany

hereafter referred to as "the Joint controller",

represented by

Prof. Dr. **, Legal Representative

Westfälische Wilhelms-Universität Universität Münster – Germany

with headquarters in Schlossplatz 2, 48149 Münster

hereinafter referred to as "the Joint controller",

represented by

Prof. Dr. **, Legal Representative

Universidade de Évora

with headquarters in Largo dos Colegiais, 2 7000-803 Évora – Portugal

hereinafter referred to as "the Joint controller",

represented by

Prof. Dr. **, Legal Representative,

Whereas:

- a) the University of Siena and the Parties named above jointly operate under the project "Counteracting accent discrimination pRactiCes in Education (CIRCE)" (GRANT AGREEMENT NUMBER: 2022-1-IT02-KA220-SCH-000087602 PROJECT CODE: 2022-1-IT02-KA220-SCH-000087602 OID E10209118 CUP B61I22000680006), of which the University of Siena is the lead partner, whose aims is to investigate accent discrimination in education, to raise awareness about accent discrimination in the school and university environment, and to develop among students and teachers a greater tolerance towards accent variation in Europe;
- b) under a partnership agreement, the Parties shall carry out personal data processing operations with respect to the collection of speech data (e.g., audio-visual recordings), written data (e.g., linguistic autobiographies), behavioural data (e.g., answers to questionnaires, response time);
- c) collected data and additional research data (e.g., perceptual, acoustical and statistical analysis) are hosted at the CNR server and, secondly, at the Siena University server (as backup copies)

Given all of the above, the Parties agree as follows:

ARTICLE 1 PROCESSING OF PERSONAL DATA

Consistent with their mission and values, the Parties mutually undertake to protect the personal data of every physical person who comes into contact or operates with them ("data subject"), respecting the identity, dignity of every human being and the fundamental rights and freedoms, and in compliance with European Regulation 2016/679 ("EU Regulation" or "GDPR") on the protection of individuals with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data ("Personal Data") and other provisions applicable to the processing.

ARTICLE 2 JOINT CONTROLLERS

Article 26 of the GDPR provides that when two or more Data Controllers jointly determine the purposes and means of the processing, they are joint controllers ("Joint Controllers"). They determine, in a transparent manner, and through an internal agreement, their respective

responsibilities regarding compliance with the obligations arising from the EU Regulation, with particular regard to the exercise of the data subject's rights, and the

respective functions of disclosure of information under Articles 13 and 14, unless and to the extent that their respective responsibilities are determined by the law of the Union or the Member State to which the data controllers' treatment are subject to. Such an agreement may designate a point of contact for data subjects (see Article 9).

The agreement adequately reflects the respective roles and relationships of the joint controllers with the data subjects.

The Parties shall essentially carry out research, dissemination and valorisation with regard to language discrimination (in particular, accentism). The Co-Parties declare, with regard to the processing of Personal Data, that they share means and purposes, facilities and resources and in particular:

- databases containing audio-visual data, written data, behavioural data (responses to questionnaires, reaction time, and related metadata);
- the purposes of personal data processing each with its own specificities related to the activities concretely carried out (see Art. 3);
- the means of processing and the manner of processing personal data;
- the data retention policy;
- the style and manner of communication of disclosures under Art. 13 of the GDPR;
- the procedure for handling any processing consents given by data subjects;
- the procedures in the case of data transfer outside the EU;
- the tools and means used for the implementation of the decisions and, in part, also for the operations of the Data Controllers, especially in relation to physical, organizational and technical security measures;
- the risk-based approach (DPIA);
- the personal data security profiles and policy and the Data Breach procedure;
- the management of the procedure for exercising the rights of the data subject.

Joint controllership refers to the Processing of Personal Data and is concerned with the processing of all data acquired during the research work (e.g., audio files and related metadata).

The Joint controllers share decisions on the purposes and means of data processing and are obliged to prepare and keep up-to-date all the compliances required by the EU Regulation and the current legal provisions on personal data protection.

Each Joint controller undertakes to prepare and keep up-to-date all required Personal Data protection compliances, including the maintenance of the processing register, pursuant to Article 30 of the GDPR.

ARTICLE 3

PERSONAL DATA PROCESSING OPERATIONS CARRIED OUT BY EACH JOINT DATA CONTROLLER

The Joint controllers carry out their tasks in accordance with the principles governing the processing of personal data, including those of purpose, proportionality, and minimization of personal data processed, and process the data of data subjects (physical persons) jointly as described below, for the purpose of the best management of the activities aimed at achieving the purposes of the processing.

Data categories	Joint controllers processing data	Data processing purposes*	Data processing means
Speech and audiovisual data (oral and AV interviews; short stories; podcasts), including special categories of personal data	The Universities of Siena, Hamburg, Evora, and Munster will collect the data and the CNR will organise such data according to the common database entries	archiving in the public interest, scientific research, public outreach	Data collection via AV digital recordings devices and data processing through software for AV data curation and analysis (e.g. Audacity, Praat)
Written autobiographies, including special categories of personal data	The Universities of Siena, Hamburg, Evora, and Munster will collect the data and the CNR will organise such data according to the common database entries	archiving in the public interest, scientific research, public outreach	Textual data collection and data processing through <i>Component MetaData Infrastructure</i> (CMDI) via COMEDI, the Web-based editor for CMDI-conformant metadata
Statistical surveys (behavioural data, such as reaction time, answers to audio stimuli)	The Universities of Siena, Hamburg, Evora, and Munster will collect the data and the CNR will organise such data according to the common database entries	archiving in the public interest, scientific research	Behavioural data collection (via Implicit Association Task test), perceptual data collection (via verbal guise technique) and data processing through statistical analysis (R program)
institutional communications (email contents and personal addresses)	The Universities of Siena, Hamburg, Evora, and Munster will send the communication	sending institutional communications to members of the project and to participants in the survey	Email exchanges
Quality surveys for internal assessment	The CNR will collect the data and will organise such data according to the common databases entries (for internal use only)	internal evaluations of the project, also carried out through questionnaires sent to students and/or members of the project in order to improve dissemination and communication activities	Email exchanges Digital written questionnaires

*Purposes of processing are understood to be pursued by each controller, except as specified in the table.

The joint controllers are directly responsible for the lawfulness of the processing within their competence. In relation to the data subjects, the joint controllers are jointly and severally liable for damages arising from the processing, without prejudice, in internal relations, to the responsibility of each controller for the activities directly attributable to the same.

ARTICLE 4 DATA RETENTION PERIOD

One of the principles applicable to the Processing of Personal Data relates to the limitation of the retention period, regulated in Article 5(1)(e) of the GDPR, which states, "Personal Data shall be kept in a form which permits the identification of Data Subjects for a period of time which does not exceed the fulfilment of the purposes for which they are processed; Personal Data may be kept for longer periods provided that they are processed solely for archiving purposes in the public interest, scientific or historical research or statistical purposes, in accordance with Article 89(1) of the EU Regulation, subject to the implementation of appropriate technical and organizational measures required by this Regulation

to protect the rights and freedoms of the data subject". The determination of the retention period is defined according to the principle of necessity of processing. Therefore, personal data will be retained for the period necessary to carry out the purposes stated in Article 3. However, personal data will be retained for the duration of the project and thereafter for as long as necessary for related scientific research.

The researchers involved in CIRCE project intend to destroy all the Participant behavioural data (including their consent forms) no later than 10 years after the start of this research project (i.e., by 31 December 2032 at the latest).

All Researchers' written notes are intended to be destroyed after they have no further practical use and no later than 10 years after the start of this research project (i.e., by 31st December 2032 at the latest).

In any case, personal data may be retained for statistical or scientific purposes even beyond the period necessary to achieve the purposes for which they were collected or subsequently processed, in accordance with Article 5(1)(e) of the GDPR.

ARTICLE 5

RECIPIENTS OF DATA PROCESSING

Data of a personal nature may be disclosed by each joint controller, with the agreement of all partners, to recipients in the following categories:

- public research institutions
- public research repositories
- journals
- conferences.

In case a joint controller intends to disclose the data to different recipients, he/she should inform the other joint controllers who shall communicate their consent/disagreement within 20 days of the communication.

ARTICLE 6

INFORMATION TO THE DATA SUBJECT

In relation to all personal data processing carried out, the joint controller who directly collects the data from the data subject undertakes to provide, at the time of data collection, the information referred to in Article 13 of the GDPR.

However, the information pursuant to Articles 13 and 14 of the GDPR will be published in the CIRCE project portal, which is under construction.

The essential content of this Joint Controllership Agreement will be made available to interested parties in the CIRCE project portal, under construction.

ARTICLE 7
AUTHORIZED PROCESSORS AND DATA CONTROLLERS

The Parties undertake to instruct and authorize individuals who are part of their organization to process personal data and to ensure compliance with applicable regulations regarding the processing of personal data within their organization.

In particular, the joint controllers undertake to:

- communicate and disseminate their policy regarding the protection of personal data;
- listen to and focus attention on all interested parties and give due consideration to their requests regarding the processing of personal data and give prompt feedback;
- process personal data lawfully, fairly and transparently in line with constitutional principles and relevant current legislation, especially with regards to EU Regulation, and only for the time strictly necessary for the intended purposes, including the compliance with legal obligations;
- collect personal data limited to those that are indispensable to carry out the activities (relevant and limited personal data);
- process personal data in accordance with the principles of transparency for only the specific purposes and expressed in its disclosures;
- adopt processes for updating and rectifying the personal data it processes to ensure that personal data is, as far as possible, correct and up-to-date;
- preserve and protect the personal data it holds with the best preservation techniques available;
- ensure that personal data protection measures are continuously updated. This commitment will be constantly followed within the framework of the principle of accountability by consistently putting in place appropriate technical and organizational measures and appropriate corporate policies that ensure and are able to demonstrate that processing is carried out in accordance with the EU Regulation, taking into account the state of the art, the nature of the personal data held and the risks to which they are exposed;
- make clear, transparent and relevant the manner in which Personal Data is processed and stored in a manner that ensures adequate security;
- provide training to its staff and collaborators, based on the task performed, on the principles of lawfulness and fairness to which this Personal Data Protection Policy and the processing of Personal Data must conform, as well as on compliance with the safeguards adopted;
- fostering the development of a sense of empowerment and awareness of the entire organization towards personal data, seen as the property of the individuals concerned;
- ensure compliance with the laws and regulations applicable to the protection of personal data by updating personal data protection management as necessary;
- prevent and minimize, consistent with available company resources, the impact of potential violations or unlawful and/or harmful processing of personal data;
- promote the inclusion of personal data protection in the continuous improvement plan that the organization pursues with its management systems.

ARTICLE 8
DATA PROCESSORS

By entering into this agreement, the joint controllers consent to the processing of personal data through the subjects already appointed, at the time of entering into this agreement, as data processors by each joint controller. After the conclusion of this agreement, each joint controller can appoint new processors.

Upon the request of another joint controller, each joint controller shall provide a list of data processor appointed by itself.

The Data Controller and the Data Processor shall ensure that any person acting under their authority and having access to personal data shall not process such data unless instructed to do so by the Data Controller, unless required to do so by Union or Member State law.

ARTICLE 9
EXERCISE OF DATA SUBJECT'S RIGHTS

The point of contact for all requests to exercise the rights under Articles 15-22 of the GDPR is the University of Siena, at the email address gdpr.circe@unisi.it.

These rights, individually enumerated below, can be exercised by the data subjects:

Right of access (as provided for by art. 15 GDPR)

Right to rectification (as provided for by art. 16 GDPR)

Right to erasure (as provided for by art. 17 GDPR)

Right to restriction of processing (as provided for by art. 18 GDPR)

Notification obligation regarding rectification or erasure of personal data or restriction of processing

Right to data portability (as provided for by art. 20 GDPR)

Right to object (as provided for by art. 21 GDPR)

Rights related to automated decision-making and profiling (as provided for by art. 22 GDPR)

Should a data subject wish to exercise any of these rights, they may contact the University of Siena directly. Information on action taken at the request of the data subject in accordance with Articles 15 - 22 GDPR shall be provide to the data subject by the University of Siena. The Data Controllers undertake to cooperate in the handling of the aforementioned requests.

In any case, the data subject may exercise his or her rights under the GDPR with respect to and against each data controller. This is without prejudice, in any case, to the possibility for the latter to exercise the right of recourse pursuant to Article 82(5) of the GDPR.

The University of Siena is legally represented by the Rector. He can be reached at: rettore@unisi.it (e-mail); rettore@pec.unisipec.it (certified email - PEC).

The Data Protection Officer is Dr **. She/He can be reached at: rpd@unisi.it (mail); [pec: rpd@pec.unisipec.it](mailto:pec:rpd@pec.unisipec.it) (certified email - PEC).

The CNR is legally represented by the Director of the Istituto di Linguistica Computazionale "Antonio Zampolli" of the Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche. She/He can be reached at: direttore@ilc.cnr.it (e-mail); protocollo.ilc@pec.cnr.it (certified email - PEC).

The Data Protection Officer can be reached at: rpd@cnr.it (mail); [pec: rpd@pec.cnr.it](mailto:pec:rpd@pec.cnr.it) (certified email - PEC).

The Universität Hamburg is legally represented by the President. He can be reached at: praesident@uni-hamburg.de.

The Data Protection Officer is **. She/He can be reached at: datenschutz@uni-hamburg.de.

The Westfälische Wilhelms-Universität Universität Münster is legally represented by a member of the rectorate, Dr. **.

She/He can be reached at: katharina.steinberg@uni-muenster.de. The Data Protection Officer is **. She/He can be reached at: datenschutz@uni-muenster.de

The Universidade de Évora is legally represented by the Rector. The Universidade de Évora is legally represented by the Vice-Rector. He can be reached at: investigar@scc.uevora.pt

The Data Protection Officer is **. She/He can be reached at: epd@uevora.pt

ARTICLE 10

PROCESSING SECURITY

Each Joint Controller is obliged to implement, in accordance with the provisions of Article 32 of the GDPR, all appropriate technical and organizational security measures to protect the personal data processed under the Joint controllership relationship, in accordance with the established security plan.

In assessing the appropriate level of security, special consideration shall be given to the risks presented by the processing that arise in particular from the destruction, loss, modification, unauthorized disclosure of or access to, whether accidental or unlawful, personal data transmitted, stored or otherwise processed.

Each Joint Controller shall regularly verify compliance with these measures and provide sufficient documentation to the other Data Controllers.

Each Joint Controller will take all technical and organizational security measures for the timely recovery of the availability of personal data in the event of a physical or technical incident.

Each Joint Controller will perform periodic monitoring of the level of security so as to alleviate any risk.

ARTICLE 11 DATA BREACH

A Data Breach is any security breach that accidentally or unlawfully results in the destruction, loss, modification, unauthorized disclosure of or access to personal data transmitted, stored or otherwise processed by the data controller.

Pursuant to and in accordance with Article 33 EU of the GDPR, in the event of a personal data breach, the data controller shall notify the competent supervisory authority of the breach without undue delay and where possible within 72 hours of becoming aware of it unless the personal data breach is unlikely to present a risk to the rights and freedoms of physical persons. Where notification is not given within 72 hours, it shall be accompanied by the reasons for delay. Pursuant to Article 34 EU of the GDPR, the data controller shall notify the data subject of the breach without undue delay if the personal data breach is likely to present a high risk to the fundamental rights and freedoms of the data subject.

The data controller for the management of any Data Breach is the Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche – ILC, which will comply with the Data Breach Management Framework. Each joint controller will therefore have to promptly notify privacy@circe-project.eu of any data breach cases for joint assessment of the phenomenon and for possible notifications to the Supervisory Authority and data subjects.

ARTICLE 12 DECISIONS REGARDING INTERNATIONAL TRANSFERS OF PERSONAL DATA

Personal Data will be processed by joint controllers within the European Economic Area. Joint controllers may appoint data processors that process data in the U.S. in compliance with the EU-U.S. Data Privacy Framework (Commission Implementing Decision of 10.7.2023 pursuant to Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council on the adequate level of protection of personal data under the EU-US Data Privacy Framework).

In the event that for research purposes it becomes necessary to transfer Personal Data outside the European Economic Area, the transfer of Personal Data, limited to the performance of specific processing activities, will be regulated in accordance with the provisions of Chapter V of the EU Regulation. The decision about the transfer will be made by mutual agreement among all the joint data subjects.

**ARTICLE 13
CONCLUSIONS**

The parties agree to revise this agreement as needed; to this end, it will be monitored and revised periodically to ensure that it is current and aligned with legislative changes.

This agreement will terminate with the achievement of the purposes of processing by the joint controllers or if the conditions for joint controllership are no longer met.

Signatures:

University of Siena	Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche
Prof. **	Dr. **
Rector, Legal representative	Director of the Istituto di Linguistica Computazionale "Antonio Zampolli", Legal representative
Signature: _____	Signature: _____
Place:	Place:
Date:	Date:

Universität Hamburg	Westfälische Wilhelms-Universität Universität Münster
Prof. Dr. **	Prof. Dr. **
President, Legal representative	Dezernentin, Legal representative
Signature: _____	Signature: _____

Place:	Place:
Date:	Date:
Universidade de Évora	
Prof. Dr. **	
Vice-Rector, Legal representative	
Signature: _____	
Place:	
Date:	

Appendix 2 - STANDARD CONTRACTUAL CLAUSES

STANDARD CONTRACTUAL CLAUSES

SECTION I

Clause 1

Purpose and scope

(a) The purpose of these standard contractual clauses is to ensure compliance with the requirements of Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data (General Data Protection Regulation) ⁽¹⁾ for the transfer of personal data to a third country.

(b) The Parties:

- (i) the natural or legal person(s), public authority/ies, agency/ies or other body/ies (hereinafter ‘entity/ies’) transferring the personal data, as listed in Annex I.A (hereinafter each ‘data exporter’), and
- (ii) the entity/ies in a third country receiving the personal data from the data exporter, directly or indirectly via another entity also Party to these Clauses, as listed in Annex I.A (hereinafter each ‘data importer’)

have agreed to these standard contractual clauses (hereinafter: 'Clauses').

(c) These Clauses apply with respect to the transfer of personal data as specified in Annex I.B.

(d) The Appendix to these Clauses containing the Annexes referred to therein forms an integral part of these Clauses.

Clause 2

Effect and invariability of the Clauses

(a) These Clauses set out appropriate safeguards, including enforceable data subject rights and effective legal remedies, pursuant to Article 46(1) and Article 46(2)(c) of Regulation (EU) 2016/679 and, with respect to data transfers from controllers to processors and/or processors to processors, standard contractual clauses pursuant to Article 28(7) of Regulation (EU) 2016/679, provided they are not modified, except to select the appropriate Module(s) or to add or update information in the Appendix. This does not prevent the Parties from including the standard contractual clauses laid down in these Clauses in a wider contract and/or to add other clauses or additional safeguards, provided that they do not contradict, directly or indirectly, these Clauses or prejudice the fundamental rights or freedoms of data subjects.

(b) These Clauses are without prejudice to obligations to which the data exporter is subject by virtue of Regulation (EU) 2016/679.

Clause 3

Third-party beneficiaries

(a) Data subjects may invoke and enforce these Clauses, as third-party beneficiaries, against the data exporter and/or data importer, with the following exceptions:

(i) Clause 1, Clause 2, Clause 3, Clause 6, Clause 7;

(ii) Clause 8 – Module One: Clause 8.5 (e) and Clause 8.9(b); Module Two: Clause 8.1(b), 8.9(a), (c), (d) and (e); Module Three: Clause 8.1(a), (c) and (d) and Clause 8.9(a), (c), (d), (e), (f) and (g); Module Four: Clause 8.1 (b) and Clause 8.3(b);

(iii) Clause 9 – Module Two: Clause 9(a), (c), (d) and (e); Module Three: Clause 9(a), (c), (d) and (e);

(iv) Clause 12 – Module One: Clause 12(a) and (d); Modules Two and Three: Clause 12(a), (d) and (f);

(v) Clause 13;

(vi) Clause 15.1(c), (d) and (e);

(vii) Clause 16(e);

(viii) Clause 18 – Modules One, Two and Three: Clause 18(a) and (b); Module Four: Clause 18.

(b) Paragraph (a) is without prejudice to rights of data subjects under Regulation (EU) 2016/679.

Clause 4

Interpretation

- (a) Where these Clauses use terms that are defined in Regulation (EU) 2016/679, those terms shall have the same meaning as in that Regulation.
- (b) These Clauses shall be read and interpreted in the light of the provisions of Regulation (EU) 2016/679.
- (c) These Clauses shall not be interpreted in a way that conflicts with rights and obligations provided for in Regulation (EU) 2016/679.

Clause 5

Hierarchy

In the event of a contradiction between these Clauses and the provisions of related agreements between the Parties, existing at the time these Clauses are agreed or entered into thereafter, these Clauses shall prevail.

Clause 6

Description of the transfer(s)

The details of the transfer(s), and in particular the categories of personal data that are transferred and the purpose(s) for which they are transferred, are specified in Annex I.B.

Clause 7 – Optional

Docking clause

- (a) An entity that is not a Party to these Clauses may, with the agreement of the Parties, accede to these Clauses at any time, either as a data exporter or as a data importer, by completing the Appendix and signing Annex I.A.
- (b) Once it has completed the Appendix and signed Annex I.A, the acceding entity shall become a Party to these Clauses and have the rights and obligations of a data exporter or data importer in accordance with its designation in Annex I.A.
- (c) The acceding entity shall have no rights or obligations arising under these Clauses from the period prior to becoming a Party.

SECTION II – OBLIGATIONS OF THE PARTIES

Clause 8

Data protection safeguards

The data exporter warrants that it has used reasonable efforts to determine that the data importer is able, through the implementation of appropriate technical and pseudonymization measures, to satisfy its obligations under these Clauses.

MODULE ONE: Transfer controller to controller

8.1 Purpose limitation

The data importer shall process the personal data only for the specific purpose(s) of the transfer, as set out in Annex I.B. It may only process the personal data for another purpose:

- (i) where it has obtained the data subject's prior consent;
- (ii) where necessary for the establishment, exercise or defence of legal claims in the context of specific administrative, regulatory or judicial proceedings; or
- (iii) where necessary in order to protect the vital interests of the data subject or of another natural person.

8.2 Transparency

(a) In order to enable data subjects to effectively exercise their rights pursuant to Clause 10, the data importer shall inform them, either directly or through the data exporter:

- (i) of its identity and contact details;
- (ii) of the categories of personal data processed;
- (iii) of the right to obtain a copy of these Clauses;
- (iv) where it intends to onward transfer the personal data to any third party/ies, of the recipient or categories of recipients (as appropriate with a view to providing meaningful information), the purpose of such onward transfer and the ground therefore pursuant to Clause 8.7.

(b) Paragraph (a) shall not apply where the data subject already has the information, including when such information has already been provided by the data exporter, or providing the information proves impossible or would involve a disproportionate effort for the data importer. In the latter case, the data importer shall, to the extent possible, make the information publicly available.

(c) On request, the Parties shall make a copy of these Clauses, including the Appendix as completed by them, available to the data subject free of charge. To the extent necessary to protect business secrets or other confidential information, including personal data, the Parties may redact part of the text of the Appendix prior to sharing a copy, but shall provide a meaningful summary where the data subject would otherwise not be able to understand its content or exercise his/her rights. On request, the Parties shall provide the data subject with the reasons for the redactions, to the extent possible without revealing the redacted information.

(d) Paragraphs (a) to (c) are without prejudice to the obligations of the data exporter under Articles 13 and 14 of Regulation (EU) 2016/679.

8.3 Accuracy and data minimisation

(a) Each Party shall ensure that the personal data is accurate and, where necessary, kept up to date. The data importer shall take every reasonable step to ensure that personal data that is inaccurate, having regard to the purpose(s) of processing, is erased or rectified without delay.

(b) If one of the Parties becomes aware that the personal data it has transferred or received is inaccurate, or has become outdated, it shall inform the other Party without undue delay.

(c) The data importer shall ensure that the personal data is adequate, relevant and limited to what is necessary in relation to the purpose(s) of processing.

8.4 Storage limitation

The data importer shall retain the personal data for no longer than necessary for the purpose(s) for which it is processed. It shall put in place appropriate technical or organisational measures to ensure compliance with this obligation, including erasure or anonymisation ⁽²⁾ of the data and all back-ups at the end of the retention period.

8.5 Security of processing

(a) The data importer and, during transmission, also the data exporter shall implement appropriate technical and organisational measures to ensure the security of the personal data, including protection against a breach of security leading to accidental or unlawful destruction, loss, alteration, unauthorised disclosure or access (hereinafter 'personal data breach'). In assessing the appropriate level of security, they shall take due account of the state of the art, the costs of implementation, the nature, scope, context and purpose(s) of processing and the risks involved in the processing for the data subject. The Parties shall in particular consider having recourse to encryption or pseudonymisation, including during transmission, where the purpose of processing can be fulfilled in that manner.

(b) The Parties have agreed on the technical and organisational measures set out in Annex II. The data importer shall carry out regular checks to ensure that these measures continue to provide an appropriate level of security.

(c) The data importer shall ensure that persons authorised to process the personal data have committed themselves to confidentiality or are under an appropriate statutory obligation of confidentiality.

(d) In the event of a personal data breach concerning personal data processed by the data importer under these Clauses, the data importer shall take appropriate measures to address the personal data breach, including measures to mitigate its possible adverse effects.

(e) In case of a personal data breach that is likely to result in a risk to the rights and freedoms of natural persons, the data importer shall without undue delay notify both the data exporter and the competent supervisory authority pursuant to Clause 13. Such notification shall contain i) a description of the nature of the breach (including, where possible, categories and approximate number of data subjects and personal data records concerned), ii) its likely consequences, iii) the measures taken or proposed to address the breach, and iv) the details of a contact point from whom more information can be obtained. To the extent it is not possible for the data importer to provide all the information at the same time, it may do so in phases without undue further delay.

(f) In case of a personal data breach that is likely to result in a high risk to the rights and freedoms of natural persons, the data importer shall also notify without undue delay the data subjects concerned of the personal data breach and its nature, if necessary in cooperation with the data exporter, together with the information referred to in paragraph I, points ii) to iv), unless the data importer has implemented measures to significantly reduce the risk to the rights or freedoms of natural persons, or notification would involve disproportionate efforts. In the latter case, the data importer shall instead issue a public communication or take a similar measure to inform the public of the personal data breach.

(g) The data importer shall document all relevant facts relating to the personal data breach, including its effects and any remedial action taken, and keep a record thereof.

8.6 Sensitive data

Where the transfer involves personal data revealing racial or ethnic origin, political opinions, religious or philosophical beliefs, or trade union membership, genetic data, or biometric data for the purpose of uniquely identifying a natural person, data concerning health or a person's sex life or sexual orientation, or data relating to criminal convictions or offences (hereinafter 'sensitive data'), the data importer shall apply specific restrictions and/or additional safeguards adapted to the specific nature of the data and the risks involved. This may include restricting the personnel permitted to access the personal data, additional security measures (such as pseudonymization) and/or additional restrictions with respect to further disclosure.

8.7 Onward transfers

The data importer shall not disclose the personal data to a third party located outside the European Union ⁽³⁾ (in the same country as the data importer or in another third country, hereinafter 'onward transfer') unless the third party is or agrees to be bound by these Clauses, under the appropriate Module. Otherwise, an onward transfer by the data importer may only take place if:

- (i) it is to a country benefitting from an adequacy decision pursuant to Article 45 of Regulation (EU) 2016/679 that covers the onward transfer;
- (ii) the third party otherwise ensures appropriate safeguards pursuant to Articles 46 or 47 of Regulation (EU) 2016/679 with respect to the processing in question;
- (iii) the third party enters into a binding instrument with the data importer ensuring the same level of data protection as under these Clauses, and the data importer provides a copy of these safeguards to the data exporter;
- (iv) it is necessary for the establishment, exercise or defence of legal claims in the context of specific administrative, regulatory or judicial proceedings;
- (v) it is necessary in order to protect the vital interests of the data subject or of another natural person; or
- (vi) where none of the other conditions apply, the data importer has obtained the explicit consent of the data subject for an onward transfer in a specific situation, after having informed him/her of its purpose(s), the identity of the recipient and the possible risks of such transfer to him/her due to the lack of appropriate data protection safeguards. In this case, the data importer shall inform the data exporter and, at the request of the latter, shall transmit to it a copy of the information provided to the data subject.

Any onward transfer is subject to compliance by the data importer with all the other safeguards under these Clauses, in particular purpose limitation.

8.8 Processing under the authority of the data importer

The data importer shall ensure that any person acting under its authority, including a processor, processes the data only on its instructions.

8.9 Documentation and compliance

(a) Each Party shall be able to demonstrate compliance with its obligations under these Clauses. In particular, the data importer shall keep appropriate documentation of the processing activities carried out under its responsibility.

(b) The data importer shall make such documentation available to the competent supervisory authority on request.

Clause 9

Use of sub-processors

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Clause 10

Data subject rights

MODULE ONE: Transfer controller to controller

(a) The data importer, where relevant with the assistance of the data exporter, shall deal with any enquiries and requests it receives from a data subject relating to the processing of his/her personal data and the exercise of his/her rights under these Clauses without undue delay and at the latest within one month of the receipt of the enquiry or request. ⁽¹⁰⁾ The data importer shall take appropriate measures to facilitate such enquiries, requests and the exercise of data subject rights. Any information provided to the data subject shall be in an intelligible and easily accessible form, using clear and plain language.

) In particular, upon request by the data subject the data importer shall, free of charge:

(i) provide confirmation to the data subject as to whether personal data concerning him/her is being processed and, where this is the case, a copy of the data relating to him/her and the information in Annex I; if personal data has been or will be onward transferred, provide information on recipients or categories of recipients (as appropriate with a view to providing meaningful information) to which the personal data has been or will be onward transferred, the purpose of such onward transfers and their ground pursuant to Clause 8.7; and provide information on the right to lodge a complaint with a supervisory authority in accordance with Clause 12(c)(i);

(ii) rectify inaccurate or incomplete data concerning the data subject;

(iii) erase personal data concerning the data subject if such data is being or has been processed in violation of any of these Clauses ensuring third-party beneficiary rights, or if the data subject withdraws the consent on which the processing is based.

(c) Where the data importer processes the personal data for direct marketing purposes, it shall cease processing for such purposes if the data subject objects to it.

(dd) The data importer shall not make a decision based solely on the automated processing of the personal data transferred (hereinafter 'automated decision'), which would produce legal effects concerning the data subject or similarly significantly affect him/her, unless with the explicit consent of the data subject or if authorised to do so under the laws of the country of destination, provided that such laws lay down suitable measures to safeguard the data subject's rights and legitimate interests. In this case, the data importer shall, where necessary in cooperation with the data exporter:

- (i) inform the data subject about the envisaged automated decision, the envisaged consequences and the logic involved; and
 - (ii) implement suitable safeguards, at least by enabling the data subject to contest the decision, express his/her point of view and obtain review by a human being.
- (e) Where requests from a data subject are excessive, in particular because of their repetitive character, the data importer may either charge a reasonable fee taking into account the administrative costs of granting the request or refuse to act on the request.
- (f) The data importer may refuse a data subject's request if such refusal is allowed under the laws of the country of destination and is necessary and proportionate in a democratic society to protect one of the objectives listed in Article 23(1) of Regulation (EU) 2016/679.
- (g) If the data importer intends to refuse a data subject's request, it shall inform the data subject of the reasons for the refusal and the possibility of lodging a complaint with the competent supervisory authority and/or seeking judicial redress.

Clause 11

Redress

- (a) The data importer shall inform data subjects in a transparent and easily accessible format, through individual notice or on its website, of a contact point authorised to handle complaints. It shall deal promptly with any complaints it receives from a data subject.

MODULE ONE: Transfer controller to controller

- (b) In case of a dispute between a data subject and one of the Parties as regards compliance with these Clauses, that Party shall use its best efforts to resolve the issue amicably in a timely fashion. The Parties shall keep each other informed about such disputes and, where appropriate, cooperate in resolving them.
- (c) Where the data subject invokes a third-party beneficiary right pursuant to Clause 3, the data importer shall accept the decision of the data subject to:
- (i) lodge a complaint with the supervisory authority in the Member State of his/her habitual residence or place of work, or the competent supervisory authority pursuant to Clause 13;
 - (ii) refer the dispute to the competent courts within the meaning of Clause 18.
- (d) The Parties accept that the data subject may be represented by a not-for-profit body, organisation or association under the conditions set out in Article 80(1) of Regulation (EU) 2016/679.
- (e) The data importer shall abide by a decision that is binding under the applicable EU or Member State law.
- (f) The data importer agrees that the choice made by the data subject will not prejudice his/her substantive and procedural rights to seek remedies in accordance with applicable laws.

Clause 12

Liability

MODULE ONE: Transfer controller to controller

- (a) Each Party shall be liable to the other Party/ies for any damages it causes the other Party/ies by any breach of these Clauses.
- (b) Each Party shall be liable to the data subject, and the data subject shall be entitled to receive compensation, for any material or non-material damages that the Party causes the data subject by breaching the third-party beneficiary rights under these Clauses. This is without prejudice to the liability of the data exporter under Regulation (EU) 2016/679.
- (c) Where more than one Party is responsible for any damage caused to the data subject as a result of a breach of these Clauses, all responsible Parties shall be jointly and severally liable and the data subject is entitled to bring an action in court against any of these Parties.
- (d) The Parties agree that if one Party is held liable under paragraph (c), it shall be entitled to claim back from the other Party/ies that part of the compensation corresponding to its/their responsibility for the damage.
- (e) The data importer may not invoke the conduct of a processor or sub-processor to avoid its own liability.

Clause 13

Supervision

MODULE ONE: Transfer controller to controller

- (a) [Where the data exporter is established in an EU Member State:] The supervisory authority with responsibility for ensuring compliance by the data exporter with Regulation (EU) 2016/679 as regards the data transfer, as indicated in Annex I.C, shall act as competent supervisory authority.

[Where the data exporter is not established in an EU Member State, but falls within the territorial scope of application of Regulation (EU) 2016/679 in accordance with its Article 3(2) and has appointed a representative pursuant to Article 27(1) of Regulation (EU) 2016/679:] The supervisory authority of the Member State in which the representative within the meaning of Article 27(1) of Regulation (EU) 2016/679 is established, as indicated in Annex I.C, shall act as competent supervisory authority.

[Where the data exporter is not established in an EU Member State, but falls within the territorial scope of application of Regulation (EU) 2016/679 in accordance with its Article 3(2) without however having to appoint a representative pursuant to Article 27(2) of Regulation (EU) 2016/679:] The supervisory authority of one of the Member States in which the data subjects whose personal data is transferred under these Clauses in relation to the offering of goods or services to them, or whose behaviour is monitored, are located, as indicated in Annex I.C, shall act as competent supervisory authority.

- (b) The data importer agrees to submit itself to the jurisdiction of and cooperate with the competent supervisory authority in any procedures aimed at ensuring compliance with these Clauses. In particular,

the data importer agrees to respond to enquiries, submit to audits and comply with the measures adopted by the supervisory authority, including remedial and compensatory measures. It shall provide the supervisory authority with written confirmation that the necessary actions have been taken.

SECTION III – LOCAL LAWS AND OBLIGATIONS IN CASE OF ACCESS BY PUBLIC AUTHORITIES

Clause 14

Local laws and practices affecting compliance with the Clauses

MODULE ONE: Transfer controller to controller

- (a) The Parties warrant that they have no reason to believe that the laws and practices in the third country of destination applicable to the processing of the personal data by the data importer, including any requirements to disclose personal data or measures authorising access by public authorities, prevent the data importer from fulfilling its obligations under these Clauses. This is based on the understanding that laws and practices that respect the essence of the fundamental rights and freedoms and do not exceed what is necessary and proportionate in a democratic society to safeguard one of the objectives listed in Article 23(1) of Regulation (EU) 2016/679, are not in contradiction with these Clauses.
- (b) The Parties declare that in providing the warranty in paragraph (a), they have taken due account in particular of the following elements:
- (i) the specific circumstances of the transfer, including the length of the processing chain, the number of actors involved and the transmission channels used; intended onward transfers; the type of recipient; the purpose of processing; the categories and format of the transferred personal data; the economic sector in which the transfer occurs; the storage location of the data transferred;
 - (ii) the laws and practices of the third country of destination– including those requiring the disclosure of data to public authorities or authorising access by such authorities – relevant in light of the specific circumstances of the transfer, and the applicable limitations and safeguards ⁽¹²⁾;
 - (iii) any relevant contractual, technical or organisational safeguards put in place to supplement the safeguards under these Clauses, including measures applied during transmission and to the processing of the personal data in the country of destination.
- (c) The data importer warrants that, in carrying out the assessment under paragraph (b), it has made its best efforts to provide the data exporter with relevant information and agrees that it will continue to cooperate with the data exporter in ensuring compliance with these Clauses.
- (d) The Parties agree to document the assessment under paragraph (b) and make it available to the competent supervisory authority on request.
- (e) The data importer agrees to notify the data exporter promptly if, after having agreed to these Clauses and for the duration of the contract, it has reason to believe that it is or has become subject to laws or practices not in line with the requirements under paragraph (a), including following a change in the laws of the third country or a measure (such as a disclosure request) indicating an application of such laws in practice that is not in line with the requirements in paragraph (a).

(f) Following a notification pursuant to paragraph (e), or if the data exporter otherwise has reason to believe that the data importer can no longer fulfil its obligations under these Clauses, the data exporter shall promptly identify appropriate measures (e.g. technical or organisational measures to ensure security and confidentiality) to be adopted by the data exporter and/or data importer to address the situation. The data exporter shall suspend the data transfer if it considers that no appropriate safeguards for such transfer can be ensured, or if instructed by the competent supervisory authority to do so. In this case, the data exporter shall be entitled to terminate the contract, insofar as it concerns the processing of personal data under these Clauses. If the contract involves more than two Parties, the data exporter may exercise this right to termination only with respect to the relevant Party, unless the Parties have agreed otherwise. Where the contract is terminated pursuant to this Clause, Clause 16(d) and (e) shall apply.

Clause 15

Obligations of the data importer in case of access by public authorities

MODULE ONE: Transfer controller to controller

15.1 Notification

- (a) The data importer agrees to notify the data exporter and, where possible, the data subject promptly (if necessary with the help of the data exporter) if it:
- (i) receives a legally binding request from a public authority, including judicial authorities, under the laws of the country of destination for the disclosure of personal data transferred pursuant to these Clauses; such notification shall include information about the personal data requested, the requesting authority, the legal basis for the request and the response provided; or
 - (ii) becomes aware of any direct access by public authorities to personal data transferred pursuant to these Clauses in accordance with the laws of the country of destination; such notification shall include all information available to the importer.
- (b) If the data importer is prohibited from notifying the data exporter and/or the data subject under the laws of the country of destination, the data importer agrees to use its best efforts to obtain a waiver of the prohibition, with a view to communicating as much information as possible, as soon as possible. The data importer agrees to document its best efforts in order to be able to demonstrate them on request of the data exporter.
- (c) Where permissible under the laws of the country of destination, the data importer agrees to provide the data exporter, at regular intervals for the duration of the contract, with as much relevant information as possible on the requests received (in particular, number of requests, type of data requested, requesting authority/ies, whether requests have been challenged and the outcome of such challenges, etc.).
- (d) The data importer agrees to preserve the information pursuant to paragraphs (a) to (c) for the duration of the contract and make it available to the competent supervisory authority on request.
- (e) Paragraphs (a) to (c) are without prejudice to the obligation of the data importer pursuant to Clause 14(e) and Clause 16 to inform the data exporter promptly where it is unable to comply with these Clauses.

15.2 Review of legality and data minimisation

- (a) The data importer agrees to review the legality of the request for disclosure, in particular whether it remains within the powers granted to the requesting public authority, and to challenge the request if, after careful assessment, it concludes that there are reasonable grounds to consider that the request is unlawful under the laws of the country of destination, applicable obligations under international law and principles of international comity. The data importer shall, under the same conditions, pursue possibilities of appeal. When challenging a request, the data importer shall seek interim measures with a view to suspending the effects of the request until the competent judicial authority has decided on its merits. It shall not disclose the personal data requested until required to do so under the applicable procedural rules. These requirements are without prejudice to the obligations of the data importer under Clause 14(e).
- (b) The data importer agrees to document its legal assessment and any challenge to the request for disclosure and, to the extent permissible under the laws of the country of destination, make the documentation available to the data exporter. It shall also make it available to the competent supervisory authority on request.
- (c) The data importer agrees to provide the minimum amount of information permissible when responding to a request for disclosure, based on a reasonable interpretation of the request.

SECTION IV – FINAL PROVISIONS

Clause 16

Non-compliance with the Clauses and termination

- (a) The data importer shall promptly inform the data exporter if it is unable to comply with these Clauses, for whatever reason.
- (b) In the event that the data importer is in breach of these Clauses or unable to comply with these Clauses, the data exporter shall suspend the transfer of personal data to the data importer until compliance is again ensured or the contract is terminated. This is without prejudice to Clause 14(f).
- (cc) The data exporter shall be entitled to terminate the contract, insofar as it concerns the processing of personal data under these Clauses, where:
- (i) the data exporter has suspended the transfer of personal data to the data importer pursuant to paragraph (b) and compliance with these Clauses is not restored within a reasonable time and in any event within one month of suspension;
 - (ii) the data importer is in substantial or persistent breach of these Clauses; or
 - (iii) the data importer fails to comply with a binding decision of a competent court or supervisory authority regarding its obligations under these Clauses.

In these cases, it shall inform the competent supervisory authority of such non-compliance. Where the contract involves more than two Parties, the data exporter may exercise this right to termination only with respect to the relevant Party, unless the Parties have agreed otherwise.

- (d) Personal data that has been transferred prior to the termination of the contract pursuant to paragraph (c) shall at the choice of the data exporter immediately be returned to the data exporter or deleted in its entirety. The same shall apply to any copies of the data. The data importer shall certify the deletion of the data to the data exporter. Until the data is deleted or returned, the data importer shall continue to

ensure compliance with these Clauses. In case of local laws applicable to the data importer that prohibit the return or deletion of the transferred personal data, the data importer warrants that it will continue to ensure compliance with these Clauses and will only process the data to the extent and for as long as required under that local law.

(e) Either Party may revoke its agreement to be bound by these Clauses where (i) the European Commission adopts a decision pursuant to Article 45(3) of Regulation (EU) 2016/679 that covers the transfer of personal data to which these Clauses apply; or (ii) Regulation (EU) 2016/679 becomes part of the legal framework of the country to which the personal data is transferred. This is without prejudice to other obligations applying to the processing in question under Regulation (EU) 2016/679.

Clause 17

Governing law

MODULE ONE: Transfer controller to controller

These Clauses shall be governed by the law of one of the EU Member States, provided such law allows for third-party beneficiary rights. The Parties agree that this shall be the law of Italy (*specify Member State*).

Clause 18

Choice of forum and jurisdiction

MODULE ONE: Transfer controller to controller

- (a) Any dispute arising from these Clauses shall be resolved by the courts of an EU Member State.
- (b) The Parties agree that those shall be the courts of Italy.
- (c) A data subject may also bring legal proceedings against the data exporter and/or data importer before the courts of the Member State in which he/she has his/her habitual residence.
- (d) The Parties agree to submit themselves to the jurisdiction of such courts.

⁽¹⁾ Where the data exporter is a processor subject to Regulation (EU) 2016/679 acting on behalf of a Union institution or body as controller, reliance on these Clauses when engaging another processor (sub-processing) not subject to Regulation (EU) 2016/679 also ensures compliance with Article 29(4) of Regulation (EU) 2018/1725 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 23 October 2018 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data by the Union institutions, bodies, offices and agencies and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Regulation (EC) No 45/2001 and Decision No 1247/2002/EC ([OJ L 295, 21.11.2018, p. 39](#)), to the extent these Clauses and the data protection obligations as set out in the contract or other legal act between the controller and the processor pursuant to Article 29(3) of Regulation (EU) 2018/1725 are aligned. This will in particular be the case where the controller and processor rely on the standard contractual clauses included in Decision 2021/915.

⁽²⁾ This requires rendering the data anonymous in such a way that the individual is no longer identifiable by anyone, in line with recital 26 of Regulation (EU) 2016/679, and that this process is irreversible.

⁽³⁾ The Agreement on the European Economic Area (EEA Agreement) provides for the extension of the European Union's internal market to the three EEA States Iceland, Liechtenstein and Norway. The Union data protection legislation, including Regulation (EU) 2016/679, is covered by the EEA Agreement and has

been incorporated into Annex XI thereto. Therefore, any disclosure by the data importer to a third party located in the EEA does not qualify as an onward transfer for the purpose of these Clauses.

⁽⁴⁾ The Agreement on the European Economic Area (EEA Agreement) provides for the extension of the European Union's internal market to the three EEA States Iceland, Liechtenstein and Norway. The Union data protection legislation, including Regulation (EU) 2016/679, is covered by the EEA Agreement and has been incorporated into Annex XI thereto. Therefore, any disclosure by the data importer to a third party located in the EEA does not qualify as an onward transfer for the purpose of these Clauses.

⁽⁵⁾ See Article 28(4) of Regulation (EU) 2016/679 and, where the controller is an EU institution or body, Article 29(4) of Regulation (EU) 2018/1725.

⁽⁶⁾ The Agreement on the European Economic Area (EEA Agreement) provides for the extension of the European Union's internal market to the three EEA States Iceland, Liechtenstein and Norway. The Union data protection legislation, including Regulation (EU) 2016/679, is covered by the EEA Agreement and has been incorporated into Annex XI thereto. Therefore, any disclosure by the data importer to a third party located in the EEA does not qualify as an onward transfer for the purposes of these Clauses.

⁽⁷⁾ This includes whether the transfer and further processing involves personal data revealing racial or ethnic origin, political opinions, religious or philosophical beliefs, or trade union membership, genetic data or biometric data for the purpose of uniquely identifying a natural person, data concerning health or a person's sex life or sexual orientation, or data relating to criminal convictions or offences.

⁽⁸⁾ This requirement may be satisfied by the sub-processor acceding to these Clauses under the appropriate Module, in accordance with Clause 7.

⁽⁹⁾ This requirement may be satisfied by the sub-processor acceding to these Clauses under the appropriate Module, in accordance with Clause 7.

⁽¹⁰⁾ That period may be extended by a maximum of two more months, to the extent necessary taking into account the complexity and number of requests. The data importer shall duly and promptly inform the data subject of any such extension.

⁽¹¹⁾ The data importer may offer independent dispute resolution through an arbitration body only if it is established in a country that has ratified the New York Convention on Enforcement of Arbitration Awards.

⁽¹²⁾ As regards the impact of such laws and practices on compliance with these Clauses, different elements may be considered as part of an overall assessment. Such elements may include relevant and documented practical experience with prior instances of requests for disclosure from public authorities, or the absence of such requests, covering a sufficiently representative time-frame. This refers in particular to internal records or other documentation, drawn up on a continuous basis in accordance with due diligence and certified at senior management level, provided that this information can be lawfully shared with third parties. Where this practical experience is relied upon to conclude that the data importer will not be prevented from complying with these Clauses, it needs to be supported by other relevant, objective elements, and it is for the Parties to consider carefully whether these elements together carry sufficient weight, in terms of their reliability and representativeness, to support this conclusion. In particular, the Parties have to take into account whether their practical experience is corroborated and not contradicted by publicly available or otherwise accessible, reliable information on the existence or absence of requests within the same sector and/or the application of the law in practice, such as case law and reports by independent oversight bodies.

APPENDIX

EXPLANATORY NOTE:

It must be possible to clearly distinguish the information applicable to each transfer or category of transfers and, in this regard, to determine the respective role(s) of the Parties as data exporter(s) and/or data importer(s). This does not necessarily require completing and signing separate appendices for each

transfer/category of transfers and/or contractual relationship, where this transparency can be achieved through one appendix. However, where necessary to ensure sufficient clarity, separate appendices should be used.

ANNEX I

A. LIST OF PARTIES

MODULE ONE: Transfer controller to controller

Data exporter(s): [*Identity and contact details of the data exporter(s) and, where applicable, of its/their data protection officer and/or representative in the European Union*]

1.

Name: Siena University

Address: Banchi di Sotto 55, 53100 Siena – Italy

represented by

Prof. Dr. **, Legal Representative, Rector

Contact person's name, position and contact details:

Dr. **. Data protection Officer. She/He can be reached at: rpd@unisi.it (mail); pec: rpd@pec.unisipec.it

Prof. Dr. Silvia Calamai. Full professor, project coordinator of the Erasmus+ KA2 Cooperation Project: “Counteracting accent discrimination pRactiCes in Education (CIRCE)” [AGREEMENT NUMBER: 2022-1-IT02-KA220-SCH-000087602 PROJECT CODE: 2022-1-IT02-KA220-SCH-000087602 OID E10209118 CUP B61I22000680006]. She can be reached at: silvia.calamai@unisi.it

Activities relevant to the data transferred under these clauses:

Linguistic research according to CIRCE project: collection of speech and audiovisual data (oral and AV interviews; short stories; podcasts), collection of written autobiographies; statistical surveys (behavioural data, such as reaction time, answers to questionnaires and audio stimuli)

Progress monitoring, partner management, identification and solution of issues and delays, coordination and orchestration of the technical work-packages: personal data of the staff (faculty and technicians), such as e-mails and telephone number (if necessary), necessary for the organization of the project and for the strict purposes of Work Package 1 (“Project management”)

Signature and date:

Role (controller/processor): controller

2.

Name: CNR – Istituto di Linguistica Computazionale “Antonio Zampolli” of the Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche

Address: Area della Ricerca del CNR di Pisa, Via Giuseppe Moruzzi 1, 56124 Pisa ITALY

represented by Dr. **, Legal Representative, Director of the Istituto di Linguistica Computazionale “Antonio Zampolli” of the Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche

Contact person’s name, position and contact details:

The Data Protection Officer can be reached at: rpd@cnr.it (mail); pec: rpd@pec.cnr.it (certified email - PEC).

Dr. Claudia Soria. Researcher, unit coordinator of the Erasmus+ KA2 Cooperation Project: “Counteracting accent dIscrimination pRactiCes in Education (CIRCE)” [AGREEMENT NUMBER: 2022-1-IT02-KA220-SCH-000087602 PROJECT CODE: 2022-1-IT02-KA220-SCH-000087602 OID E10209118 CUP B61I22000680006] She can be reached at: claudia.soria@ilc.cnr.it

Activities relevant to the data transferred under these clauses:

Linguistic research according to CIRCE project: description of speech and audiovisual data (oral and AV interviews; short stories; podcasts), description of written autobiographies; statistical surveys (behavioural data, such as reaction time, answers to questionnaires and audio stimuli)

Progress monitoring, quality management, identification and solution of issues and delays, implementation of the technical work-packages: personal data of the staff (faculty and technicians), such as e-mails and telephone number (if necessary), necessary for the organization of the project and for the strict purposes of Work Package 1 (“Project management”)

Signature and date:

Role (controller/processor): controller

3.

Name: Universität Hamburg

Address: Mittelweg 177 20148 Hamburg – Germany

represented by

Prof. Dr. **, Legal Representative President of Universität Hamburg

Contact person’s name, position and contact details:

Dr. **. Data protection Officer. She/He can be reached at: datenschutz@uni-hamburg.de (mail)

Prof. Dr. Robert Fuchs. Associate professor, unit coordinator and WP2 coordinator of the Erasmus+ KA2 Cooperation Project: “Counteracting accent dIscrimination pRactiCes in Education (CIRCE)” [AGREEMENT NUMBER: 2022-1-IT02-KA220-SCH-000087602

PROJECT CODE: 2022-1-IT02-KA220-SCH-000087602 OID E10209118

CUP B61I22000680006] He can be reached at: robert.fuchs@uni-hamburg.de

Prof. Dr. ** Fakultät für Geisteswissenschaften Institut für Germanistik

She/He can be reached at: **

Activities relevant to the data transferred under these clauses:

Linguistic research according to CIRCE project: collection of speech and audiovisual data (oral and AV interviews; short stories; podcasts), collection of written autobiographies; statistical surveys (behavioural data, such as reaction time, answers to questionnaires and audio stimuli)

Progress monitoring, identification and solution of issues and delays, implementation of the technical work-packages: personal data of the staff (faculty and technicians), such as e-mails and telephone number (if necessary), necessary for the organization of the project and for the strict purposes of Work Package 1 (“Project management”)

Signature and date:

Role (controller/processor): controller

4.

Name: Westfälische Wilhelms-Universität Universität Münster

Address: Schlossplatz 2, 48149 Münster

represented by

Dr. **, Dezernentin, Legal representative

Contact person's name, position and contact details:

Dr. **. Data protection Officer. She/He can be reached at: datenschutz@uni-muenster.de (mail)

Prof. Dr. Frauke Matz. Full professor, unit coordinator of the Erasmus+ KA2 Cooperation Project: “Counteracting accent discrimination pRactiCes in Education (CIRCE)” [AGREEMENT NUMBER: 2022-1-IT02-KA220-SCH-000087602 PROJECT CODE: 2022-1-IT02-KA220-SCH-000087602 OID E10209118 CUP B61I22000680006] She can be reached at: frauke.matz@uni-muenster.de

Activities relevant to the data transferred under these clauses:

Linguistic research according to CIRCE project: collection of speech and audiovisual data (oral and AV interviews; short stories; podcasts), collection of written autobiographies; statistical surveys (behavioural data, such as reaction time, answers to questionnaires and audio stimuli)

Progress monitoring, identification and solution of issues and delays, implementation of the technical work-packages: personal data of the staff (faculty and technicians), such as e-mails and telephone number (if necessary), necessary for the organization of the project and for the strict purposes of Work Package 1 (“Project management”)

Signature and date:

Role (controller/processor): controller

5.

Name: Universidade de Évora

Address: Largo dos Colegiais, 2 7000-803 Évora – Portugal

represented by

Prof. Dr. **, Legal Representative, Vice-Rector

Contact person's name, position and contact details:

Prof. **. Data protection Officer. She/He can be reached at: epd@uevora.pt (mail)

Prof. Dr. Luís Guerra. Associate professor, unit coordinator and WP3 leader of the Erasmus+ KA2 Cooperation Project: “Counteracting accent discrimination pRactiCes in Education (CIRCE)” [AGREEMENT NUMBER: 2022-1-IT02-KA220-SCH-000087602 PROJECT CODE: 2022-1-IT02-KA220-SCH-000087602 OID E10209118 CUP B61I22000680006]

He can be reached at: lspg@uevora.pt

Activities relevant to the data transferred under these clauses:

Linguistic research according to CIRCE project: collection of speech and audiovisual data (oral and AV interviews; short stories; podcasts), collection of written autobiographies; statistical surveys (behavioural data, such as reaction time, answers to questionnaires and audio stimuli)

Progress monitoring, identification and solution of issues and delays, implementation of the technical work-packages: personal data of the staff (faculty and technicians), such as e-mails and telephone number (if necessary), necessary for the organization of the project and for the strict purposes of Work Package 1 (“Project management”)

Signature and date:

Role (controller/processor): controller

Data importer(s): *[Identity and contact details of the data importer(s), including any contact person with responsibility for data protection]*

Name: International Burch University

Address: Francuske revolucije bb, 71210 Ilidža, Sarajevo

represented by Prof. Dr. **, Legal representative, Rector

Contact persons' names, position and contact details:

Mr. Senahid Kahteran. Data protection officer. He can be reached at senahid.kahteran@ibu.edu.ba

Prof. Dr. Amna Brdarević-Čeljo. unit coordinator and WP4 coordinator of the Erasmus+ KA2 Cooperation Project: "Counteracting accent discrimination practices in Education (CIRCE)" [AGREEMENT NUMBER: 2022-1-IT02-KA220-SCH-000087602

PROJECT CODE: 2022-1-IT02-KA220-SCH-000087602 OID E10209118

CUP B61I22000680006]. She can be reached at amna.brdarevic.celjo@ibu.edu.ba

Activities relevant to the data transferred under these Clauses:

Linguistic research according to CIRCE project: collection of speech and audiovisual data (oral and AV interviews; short stories; podcasts), collection of written autobiographies; statistical surveys (behavioural data, such as reaction time, answers to questions and audio stimuli)

Progress monitoring, identification and solution of issues and delays, implementation of the technical work-packages: personal data of the staff (faculty and technicians), such as e-mails and telephone number (if necessary), necessary for the organization of the project and for the strict purposes of Work Package 1 ("Project management")

Signature and date:

Role (controller/processor): controller

B. DESCRIPTION OF TRANSFER

MODULE ONE: Transfer controller to controller

Categories of data subjects whose personal data is transferred

Secondary schools and University students; teachers in secondary schools; professors and researchers at university

Categories of personal data transferred

Personal data (e.g., age, place of birth and place of living, nationality, sex, personal voice and personal images, opinion and attitudes about use of languages)

Sensitive data transferred (if applicable) and applied restrictions or safeguards that fully take into consideration the nature of the data and the risks involved, such as for instance strict purpose limitation, access restrictions (including access only for staff having followed specialised training), keeping a record of access to the data, restrictions for onward transfers or additional security measures.

Data revealing racial or ethnic origin, religious or philosophical beliefs (Audiovisual data and linguistic autobiographies)

Applied restrictions: strict purpose limitation, access restrictions (private website with access only for research members of the project)

The frequency of the transfer (e.g. whether the data is transferred on a one-off or continuous basis).

The frequency of the transfer is connected to the single research activity pursued by the project, as outlined in the description of the single Work package and in the Data Management Plan (accessible at the following address: www.circe-project.eu/)

Nature of the processing

Collection, recording, organisation, structuring, storage, consultation, use, dissemination

Purpose(s) of the data transfer and further processing

Archiving in the public interest, scientific research, public outreach

Personal data of the staff (faculty and technicians), such as e-mails and telephone number (if necessary), will be used only for the organization of the project and for the strict purposes of Work Package 1, which are devoted to “Project management”, and can be summarized as follows: Progress monitoring, partner management, quality management, identification and solution of issues and delays, coordination and orchestration of the technical work-packages.

The period for which the personal data will be retained, or, if that is not possible, the criteria used to determine that period

The determination of the retention period is defined according to the principle of necessity of processing. Therefore, personal data will be retained for the period necessary to carry out the research activities stated in the Project. However, personal data will be retained for the duration of the project and thereafter for as long as necessary for related scientific research.

The researchers involved in CIRCE project intend to destroy all the Participant behavioural data (including their consent forms) no later than 10 years after the start of this research project (i.e., by 31 December 2032 at the latest).

All Researchers’ written notes are intended to be destroyed after they have no further practical use and no later than 10 years after the start of this research project (i.e., by 31st December 2032 at the latest).

In any case, personal data may be retained for statistical or scientific purposes even beyond the period necessary to achieve the purposes for which they were collected or subsequently processed, in accordance with Article 5, (1) letter e) of Regulation (EU) 2016/679.

For transfers to (sub-) processors, also specify subject matter, nature and duration of the processing

International Burch University ensures that data will not be transferred to sub-processor.

C. COMPETENT SUPERVISORY AUTHORITY

MODULE ONE: Transfer controller to controller

Identify the competent supervisory authority/ies in accordance with Clause 13

Garante per la Protezione dei Dati personali – Italian Data Supervisory Authority

ANNEX II

TECHNICAL AND ORGANISATIONAL MEASURES INCLUDING TECHNICAL AND ORGANISATIONAL MEASURES TO ENSURE THE SECURITY OF THE DATA

MODULE ONE: Transfer controller to controller

EXPLANATORY NOTE:

The technical and organisational measures must be described in specific (and not generic) terms. See also the general comment on the first page of the Appendix, in particular on the need to clearly indicate which measures apply to each transfer/set of transfers.

Description of the technical and organisational measures implemented by the data importer(s) (including any relevant certifications) to ensure an appropriate level of security, taking into account the nature, scope, context and purpose of the processing, and the risks for the rights and freedoms of natural persons.

<i>Technical and organisational measures</i>	<i>Description</i>
<i>Measures of pseudonymisation and encryption of personal data</i>	<p>Data collected during fieldwork</p> <p>Data will be treated with utmost protection, using a dissociation process to separate it from data subjects’ identities. A dissociation file will link participant identities with unique identifiers, kept separate from project data. Each partner will have access to its own dissociation file, which will not be shared with any other partner. Both data and metadata, including participants’ personal information, will be coded using participant numbers in tests and data tables so as to ensure pseudo-anonymity, and publications will employ arbitrary subject numbers. All physical documents will be stored securely in locked closets and digital files will be kept in a controlled environment with authorized access. Researchers will sign confidentiality agreements. Personal data will be retained only for the period necessary to carry out the purposes of the</p>

	project, while pseudo-anonymized data will be preserved for future research with participant consent.
<i>Measures for ensuring physical security of locations at which personal data are processed</i>	<p>Data Storage</p> <p>International Burch University will have access to the data stored within the ILC4CLARIN archive and to the protected sections of the website.</p> <p>All data stored within the ILC4CLARIN archive will be protected according to the Code of Conduct for Service Providers, a common protection standard for the research and higher education sector. Moreover, ILC4CLARIN's storage plan offers the following features against data loss:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • all data in the repository will be kept in at least three copies, one of which off-site, at all times; • all the copies will be checked regularly and replaced, should any of them become corrupted.
Measures for ensuring data minimisation	<p>In managing data, advanced measures to ensure the security of personal data and strict adherence to data protection guidelines are employed.</p> <p>Only essential information required for specific purposes are collected, ensuring that data is kept to a minimum. This not only safeguards user privacy but also reduces the risk of excessive data collection.</p>
Measures for ensuring data quality	<p>Validation and data verification processes during registration to the protected area in the website are implemented, since each enregistration need to be approved by a data controller: this procedure ensures that data is accurate, complete, and up-to-date, and avoids the inclusion of outdated or inaccurate information.</p>
Measures for ensuring limited data retention	<p>Stringent unused data deletion and archiving policies are applied. Data is retained only for the period necessary for the stated purposes and is promptly deleted in compliance with applicable regulations.</p>
Measures for the protection of data during storage	<p>As for data transfer and archiving AES-256 encryption in conjunction with SSL/TLS are used, to protect data transmission during user registration and account access. Using password protected backup with AES-256 encryption is an advanced encryption standard that ensures a high level of data security during both transmission and storage. page on the website are provided.</p>
Measures for allowing data portability and ensuring erasure	<p>Users' rights to access their data at any time and request its deletion are respected. Procedures and tools to allow users to exercise these rights easily and directly through the personal profile</p>

Measures for ensuring physical security of locations at which personal data are processed	Physical access to data is strictly controlled and limited to authorized personnel, using badges for identification. All accesses and/or changes to data are meticulously tracked.
Measures for ensuring events logging	This tracking is done through system logs (server logs) and the use of specific plugins that record the activities of registered users. The recorded activities are centrally stored in a separate database table, allowing constant surveillance of the environment and prompt response to any suspicious activities.
Measures for ensuring system configuration, including default configuration	In order to provide a secure and compliant computing environment, system configuration management, together with regular updates and advanced configuration, is regular applied.
Measures for internal IT and IT security governance and management	Access to systems which store and process Personal Data is subject to role based need. Employees have individual logins for such systems. Two-factor authentication is enabled if needed/upon request. Technical controls and policies are in place to ensure Personal Data is never held on end user devices of Employees, or otherwise transferred by Employees to unauthorised systems. Security and privacy awareness takes place during onboarding and on an ongoing basis. Employees are subject to regular audits to ensure adherence to our information security policy.

[Examples of possible measures:

Measures of pseudonymisation and encryption of personal data

Measures for ensuring ongoing confidentiality, integrity, availability and resilience of processing systems and services

Measures for ensuring the ability to restore the availability and access to personal data in a timely manner in the event of a physical or technical incident

Processes for regularly testing, assessing and evaluating the effectiveness of technical and organisational measures in order to ensure the security of the processing

Measures for user identification and authorisation

Measures for the protection of data during transmission

Measures for the protection of data during storage

Measures for ensuring physical security of locations at which personal data are processed

Measures for ensuring events logging

Measures for ensuring system configuration, including default configuration

Measures for internal IT and IT security governance and management

Measures for certification/assurance of processes and products

Measures for ensuring data minimisation

Measures for ensuring data quality

Measures for ensuring limited data retention

Measures for ensuring accountability

Measures for allowing data portability and ensuring erasure]

For transfers to (sub-) processors, also describe the specific technical and organisational measures to be taken by the (sub-) processor to be able to provide assistance to the controller and, for transfers from a processor to a sub-processor, to the data exporter

Appendix 3

Transfer Impact Assessment (TIA)

Transfer Impact Assessment – TIA

The parties has to fulfill the requirements according to Art. 14 b SCC:

(i) the specific circumstances of the transfer, including the length of the processing chain, the number of actors involved and the transmission channels used; intended onward transfers; the type of recipient; the purpose of processing; the categories and format of the transferred personal data; the economic sector in which the transfer occurs; the storage location of the data transferred;

The specific circumstances of the transfer are strictly connected to the objectives of the research project CIRCE and its workpackages (in particular, WP2 “Raising awareness on accent discrimination”, and WP4 “Engaging students in self-reflective practices”; WP3 “Empowering teachers with innovative material for preventing accent discrimination” does not involve personal data transfer, while WP1 “Management” is a compulsory WP in all the Erasmus+ projects). The transfer occurs in the field of speech sciences in the academic domain. A description of the project is available at <https://www.circe-project.eu/>, where also the Data Management Plan and the CIRCE Code of Conduct can be downloaded.

At the beginning of the project, a *Data Management Plan* was defined (the version 0.1 is uploaded on the Zenodo repository [DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.10085133] and made easily accessible also via the CIRCE website). In addition, a *Code of conduct* has been published (the original version in English – also accessible via Zenodo repository <https://zenodo.org/records/8344052> - has been

translated into all the national languages of the partners involved). Also the *Code of conduct* is accessible via the CIRCE website.

The actors involved in the transfer are the academic institutions members of the CIRCE project. All the information on the transmission channels, the type of recipient, the purpose of processing, the categories and format of the transferred personal data, the storage location of the data transferred are in the Data Management Plan:

section 1.1. (Dataset description)

section 3.1 (Fair data)

section 4.1 (Data Center Archive Storage)

section 5.1 (Data security)

section 6.1 (Ethical aspects)

In CIRCE project, controllership stems from an analysis of the factual elements described in the research project. The rationale for the choice can be summarised as follows.

The use of a common data processing system or infrastructure (like the one provided by ILC-CNR, described in the Data Management Plan) does not lead to qualifying all the parties involved as joint controllers. In particular, the Bosnian partner determines autonomously the means and the purposes of the processing. Accordingly, it was decided to separate the EU-Country Universities from the Non-EU- Country Universities.

JCA among EU countries:

Joint participation of USiena, ILC-CNR, UH, UM, UE in the determination of the purposes and means of a processing operation with respect to WP2 (“Raising awareness on accent discrimination”): UH is the WP leader, ILC-CNR is the responsible for the digital repository and the protected section of the website. UNISI is the responsible for the ethical and legal issues and proposes strategies to protect the personal data of interviewees and interviewers in the project. UBurch has no role in the determination of the purposes and means of a processing operation with respect to WP2. UBurch will upload the material collected for WP2 in the ILC-CNR repository in a pseudo-anonymized form. Statistical analysis will be carried out by UH. Universities in EU-countries will be the only controller of the processing for the purpose of analysis and statistics of the WP2 processed data, because UH determines the purpose for the processing, and has decided how the processing will be organised (experimental design, statistical analysis on pseudo-anonymized data).

As already mentioned, WP3 does not involve personal data transfer.

With respect to WP4 (“Engaging students in self-reflective practices”), and in particular Activity 1 (Podcasts CIRCECAST: Multilingual podcasts on accent discrimination’ raising awareness of accent discrimination and recounting experiences of discriminatory behaviour) and Activity 3 Contest (Videos recounting real experiences of accent discrimination and short stories/poems promoting ways of inclusive behaviors and actions to combat discrimination), UBurch will determine autonomously the purposes and means of the processing of personal data, selecting audio/videos participants, editing the audio/visual documents, establishing the format and duration of audio/visual documents, and the ways of processing data for the purposes of this WP. It remains responsible for the implementation of appropriate technical and organisational measures to ensure and be able to demonstrate that the processing is performed in accordance with EU Regulation, limited to a particular stage in the processing (e.g., editing of the podcast, evaluation of the podcast, evaluation of the contest). The contents created by UBurch will be shared with European partners. Each EU partners will use those contents for the project, determining means and purposes of this further processing (for dissemination and teaching activities) autonomously from UBurch.

With regard to WP1, personal data, such as e-mails and telephone number (if necessary), will be transferred to the UBurch within the limits of what is necessary for the organization of the project and for the strict purposes of Working Package 1, which are devoted to “Project management”, and can be summarized as follows: Progress monitoring, partner management, identification and solution of issues and delays, coordination and orchestration of the technical work-packages and liaison with other projects and with the National Agency.

The exchange of the same data or set of data from EU-countries to UBurch is therefore considered as a transmission of data between separate controllers. UBurch, as controller for its own processing activities, is responsible for ensuring the accuracy of the data it processed previously.

Additional relevant information can be found in the **Standard Contractual Rules – ANNEX II TECHNICAL AND ORGANISATIONAL MEASURES INCLUDING TECHNICAL AND ORGANISATIONAL MEASURES TO ENSURE THE SECURITY OF THE DATA.**

(ii) the laws and practices of the third country of destination – including those requiring the disclosure of data to public authorities or authorising access by such authorities – relevant in light of the specific circumstances of the transfer, and the applicable limitations and safeguards ;

This information can be found in the document provided by Bosnian research unit (entitled “PREPARATORY DOCUMENT ON BOSNIAN LEGISLATION CONCERNING PERSONAL DATA PROTECTION”).

(iii) any relevant contractual, technical or organisational safeguards put in place to supplement the safeguards under these Clauses, including measures applied during transmission and to the processing of the personal data in the country of destination.

Due to the legal situation, no further guarantees (apart from the general safeguards already required under Art. 32 GDPR) are necessary.

Appendix 4

Allegato 1 - Scheda di analisi per progetti di ricerca

Descrizione del progetto	
1. Data di inizio prevista	
2. Data di fine prevista	
3. Ipotesi/Breve stato dell'arte/justificazione teorica	
4. Obiettivi/Risultati attesi	
5. Metodologia	
Soggetti coinvolti nel Progetto	
6. Titolare	
7. Responsabile scientifico	
8. Personale coinvolto	
9. È necessaria l'autorizzazione di altri Enti/soggetti terzi per l'accesso ai dati o per il coinvolgimento	<ul style="list-style-type: none"><input type="radio"/> SI<input type="radio"/> NO <p><i>Se sì, allegare copia della lettera di autorizzazione e/o la lettera di richiesta di eventuali dati provenienti da soggetti terzi)</i></p>

<p>10. Sono previsti, ai sensi della normativa vigente, interventi che richiedono specifiche professionalità (ad es. medico, psicologo, infermiere, ecc.)?</p>	<p> <input type="radio"/> SI <input type="radio"/> NO </p> <p><i>Se sì, specificare quali istruzioni sono fornite in merito al trattamento dei dati personali</i></p>
<p>11. Ci sono eventuali partner, enti, sponsor o finanziatori che potrebbero venire a conoscenza dei dati personali?</p>	<p> <input type="radio"/> SI <input type="radio"/> NO </p> <p>Se sì, indicare tali soggetti e il ruolo che hanno del progetto</p> <p>_____</p> <p>_____</p>

Tipologia di dati trattati
<p>12. Selezionare la tipologia di dati trattati</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Dati personali: qualsiasi informazione riguardante una persona fisica identificata o identificabile («interessato»); si considera identificabile la persona fisica che può essere identificata, direttamente o indirettamente, con particolare riferimento a un identificativo come il nome, un numero di identificazione, dati relativi all'ubicazione, un identificativo online o a uno o più elementi caratteristici della sua identità fisica, fisiologica, genetica, psichica, economica, culturale o sociale.</p> <p>Tra i dati personali in particolare si raccolgono:</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> <u>Dati identificativi</u>: dati personali che permettono l'identificazione diretta.</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Categorie particolari di dati (ex Dati sensibili): dati personali che rivelino l'origine razziale o etnica, le opinioni politiche, le convinzioni religiose o filosofiche, o l'appartenenza sindacale, dati genetici, dati biometrici intesi a identificare in modo univoco una persona fisica, dati relativi alla salute o alla vita sessuale o all'orientamento sessuale della persona;</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> <u>Dati genetici</u>: dati personali relativi alle caratteristiche genetiche ereditarie o acquisite di una persona fisica che forniscono informazioni univoche sulla fisiologia o sulla salute di detta persona fisica, e che risultano in particolare dall'analisi di un campione biologico della persona fisica in questione;</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> <u>Dati biometrici</u>: dati personali ottenuti da un trattamento tecnico specifico relativi alle caratteristiche fisiche, fisiologiche o comportamentali di una persona fisica che ne consentono o confermano l'identificazione univoca, quali l'immagine facciale o i dati dattiloscopici;</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> <u>Dati relativi alla salute</u>: dati personali attinenti alla salute fisica o mentale di una persona fisica, compresa la prestazione di servizi, di assistenza sanitaria che rivelano informazioni relative al suo stato di salute.</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Dati giudiziari: dati personali che possono rivelare l'esistenza di determinati provvedimenti giudiziari soggetti ad iscrizione nel casellario giudiziale o la qualità di imputato o di indagato.</p>

Dati anonimi: informazioni che non si riferiscono ad una persona fisica identificata o identificabile o a dati personali resi sufficientemente anonimi da impedire o da non consentire più l'identificazione dell'interessato.

Partecipanti al progetto

<p>13. Tipologia</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Studenti ○ Adulti in grado di esprimere il loro consenso ○ Minori di età compresa fra i ... e i ... anni/mesi ○ Studenti lavoratori ○ Collaboratori ○ Soggetti con disabilità fisica e psichica o con limitata capacità d'intendere o volere ○ Soci, associati, aderenti o iscritti a organizzazioni a carattere religioso, politico, filosofico o sindacale ○ Condannati, detenuti, imputati, indagati o sottoposti a misure di sicurezza o prevenzione ○ Volontari sani ○ Pazienti Persone per le quali non è possibile predeterminare una specifica tipologia (ad es., somministrazione questionari via internet) ○ Altri (specificare) <hr/> <hr/>
<p>14. Numero indicativo di partecipanti</p>	<p>n. _____</p>
<p>15. Caratteristiche del gruppo di partecipanti alla ricerca</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Gruppi omogenei per abitudini sessuali ○ Gruppi omogenei per appartenenza razziale o etnica ○ Gruppi omogenei per area geografica ○ Gruppi omogenei per livello di formazione ○ Gruppi omogenei per caratteristiche fisiche ○ Gruppi omogenei per consanguineità ○ Gruppi omogenei per fattori di rischio ○ Gruppi omogenei per convinzioni religiose, filosofiche, politiche o sindacali <p>Specificare eventuali e ulteriori criteri di inclusione/esclusione</p> <hr/> <hr/>
<p>16. È possibile che alcuni dei soggetti si trovino in una</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ SI ○ NO

<p>posizione di dipendenza nei confronti del ricercatore o dei suoi collaboratori, tale per cui si possa supporre che l'espressione del consenso a partecipare allo studio non sia del tutto libera e priva da ogni tipo di pressione?</p>	<p>Se sì, indicare come si intende provvedere per minimizzare la possibilità che il soggetto si senta obbligato a prendere parte alla ricerca (ad es. nel rapporto studente/professore, paziente/medico, dipendente/datore di lavoro) <i>Esempio: Il soggetto valuta senza alcuna fretta o pressione psicologica le informazioni ricevute tramite i moduli e decide di aderire alla ricerca, fornendo il consenso al trattamento dei dati, solo in un momento successivo alla cura/incontro informativo</i></p> <hr/> <hr/>
<p>17. Come verranno diffuse le informazioni/l'invito a partecipare alla ricerca?</p>	<hr/> <hr/> <hr/>
<p>18. È prevista qualche forma di incentivo per i partecipanti allo studio?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="radio"/> SI <input type="radio"/> NO <p>Se sì, indicare quali</p> <hr/> <hr/>

<p>19. Rischi per i partecipanti</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="radio"/> Nessuno <input type="radio"/> Rischi sociali, legali o economici <input type="radio"/> Disagi o rischi per il benessere fisico e psicologico <input type="radio"/> altro (specificare) <hr/> <hr/>
<p>20. Benefici per i partecipanti</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="radio"/> Nessuno <input type="radio"/> Benefici di natura sociale ottenuti attraverso un miglioramento delle conoscenze scientifiche <input type="radio"/> Compenso o altri vantaggi materiali <input type="radio"/> altro (specificare) <hr/> <hr/>

<p>21. È prevista una specifica polizza di assicurazione per responsabilità civile aggiuntiva a quella di Ateneo? [Da compilare soprattutto nel caso di sperimentazioni mediche]</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Sì, è stata stipulata una polizza assicurativa che copre tutti i danni strettamente connessi alla partecipazione allo studio. La copertura assicurativa è stata stipulata con la seguente compagnia assicurativa: <i>Denominazione</i> <i>Numero polizza assicurativa</i> ○ Lo studio è no-profit e osservazionale e viene utilizzata l'assicurazione d'Ateneo ○ Lo studio è no-profit, interventistico e viene aggiunto un premio assicurativo ○ Non è prevista alcuna forma di assicurazione
<p>22. Come si prevede di affrontare il caso in cui l'interessato intenda non aderire alla ricerca (anche in un momento successivo)?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ L'interessato potrà ritirare il consenso in qualsiasi momento e senza fornire spiegazioni alcune, con la conseguente distruzione dei dati ○ L'interessato potrà richiedere che tutti i dati precedentemente raccolti siano distrutti o resi anonimi in modo definitivo solo nelle fasi antecedenti alla irreversibile anonimizzazione o aggregazione ○ altro (specificare) <hr/> <hr/>

Modalità e procedure	
<p>23. Modalità di raccolta dei dati</p>	<p><input type="checkbox"/> DIRETTA</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ utilizzo di questionari ○ interviste strutturate o semi-strutturate ○ interviste in profondità ○ focus group ○ raccolta di diari (diary keeping) ○ osservazione del comportamento dei soggetti a loro insaputa ○ osservazione del comportamento dei soggetti ○ ○ registrazioni audio o video dei soggetti ○ somministrazione di stimoli, compiti o procedure e registrazione di risposte comportamentali, opinioni o giudizi ○ somministrazione di stimoli, compiti o procedure che il soggetto potrebbe trovare fastidiosi, stressanti, fisicamente o psicologicamente dolorosi, sia durante sia successivamente la conduzione dello studio ○ registrazione di movimenti ○ immersione in ambienti di realtà virtuale ○ registrazione di potenziali evocati

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ somministrazione di test, questionari o protocolli sperimentali attraverso internet (web, posta elettronica) ○ utilizzo di test neuropsicologici e di tecniche di neuroimmagine ○ somministrazione di sostanze o agenti (ad es., farmaci, alcol) ○ partecipazione ad un trial clinico ○ altro (specificare) <hr/> <hr/> <p><input type="checkbox"/> INDIRETTA Il dato relativo al partecipante viene fornito da altri (ad esempio tramite richiesta di comunicazione di dati ad altro ente, questionari sottoposti a familiari e/o ad altri soggetti terzi; si prega di specificare)</p> <p><i>Effettuare una descrizione accurata della procedura - con particolare riferimento alle operazioni di raccolta dei dati. Allegare copia delle domande che verranno poste (se previsto dalla procedura utilizzata); ove questo non sia possibile, indicare gli argomenti che verranno trattati.</i></p> <hr/> <hr/> <hr/>
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Comunicazione e diffusione dei dati	
<p>24. I dati personali (non anonimi o aggregati) vengono diffusi?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ NO ○ Sì <p>Se sì, selezionare una o più modalità:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Stampa quotidiana e periodica anche elettronica ○ Stampati in genere ○ TV ○ Posta ○ Fax ○ Posta elettronica ○ Internet ○ A mezzo confezione del prodotto ○ Affissione dei dati in luoghi pubblici ○ Radio ○ Telefono

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Televideo ○ Agenzie di stampa ○ Strumenti multimediali (cd, dvd...) ○ Altro, specificare in dettaglio <hr/>
<p>25. Il titolare del trattamento si avvarrà di responsabili del trattamento?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ NO ○ Sì <p>Se sì, indicare i responsabili del trattamento e le nomine a responsabile. Se si intende avvalersi di un responsabile ma non è stato ancora individuato, indicare le modalità di nomina.</p>
<p>26. Vi sono situazioni di contitolarità?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ NO ○ Sì <p>Se sì, indicare i soggetti contitolari e gli accordi di contitolarità conclusi.</p>
<p>27. I dati personali (pseudonimizzati e che non siano pertanto anonimi o aggregati) vengono comunicati?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ NO ○ SI <p>Se sì, selezionare uno o più ambiti di comunicazione:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Soggetti privati ○ Soggetti pubblici ○ Persone giuridiche, società di persone o di capitali, imprese individuali ○ Organi costituzionali o di rilevanza costituzionale ○ Amministrazioni dello Stato ○ Amministrazioni regionali ○ Enti locali (comuni e province) ○ Associazioni di enti locali ○ Altre amministrazioni ed enti pubblici ○ Organismi del servizio sanitario nazionale ○ Enti pubblici non economici ○ Enti pubblici economici ○ Autorità giudiziaria ○ Uffici giudiziari ○ Società di vigilanza private ○ Società controllanti, controllate e/o collegate ○ Associazioni di imprenditori o di imprese ○ Organismi sindacali o patronali ○ Organismi paritetici in materia di lavoro ○ Consulenti e liberi professionisti anche in forma associata ○ Banche ○ Intermediari finanziari ○ Gestori di sistemi informatici centralizzati (centrali rischi, antifrode, ecc.) ○ Assicurazioni

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Soci associati e iscritti ○ Clienti e/o utenti ○ Altro, specificare in dettaglio
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Trasferimenti di dati all'estero (extra UE)	
<p>28. I dati personali (pseudonimizzati e che non siano pertanto anonimi o aggregati) vengono trasferiti all'estero?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ NO ○ Si <p>Se sì, in che area geografica sono trasferiti i dati?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Paesi dell'America del centro-nord ○ Paesi dell'America del sud ○ Paesi dell'area asiatica ○ Paesi dell'area africana ○ Paesi dell'Oceania ○ Paesi dell'Europa extra UE <p>Specificare il/i Paese/i all'interno dell'area indicata</p> <hr style="width: 100%;"/>

Informativa e consenso	
<p>29. È stata prevista adeguata informativa per i partecipanti?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ NO ○ Si <p><i>Se sì, allegare una copia dell'Informativa e dell'eventuale dichiarazione di consenso</i></p>
<p>30. È possibile fornire l'informativa ai partecipanti alla ricerca (soggetti interessati)?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ SI Indicare come verrà fornita l'Informativa privacy ai partecipanti al progetto ai sensi dell'art. 13 del Regolamento EU 2016/679 ○ NO Nel caso di ricerca medica, biomedica ed epidemiologica, indicare le ragioni, considerate del tutto particolari o eccezionali, documentate nel progetto di ricerca: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ No, per motivi etici riconducibili alla circostanza che l'interessato ignora la propria condizione (Rientrano in questa categoria le ricerche per le quali l'informativa sul trattamento dei dati da rendere agli interessati comporterebbe la rivelazione di notizie concernenti la conduzione dello studio la cui conoscenza potrebbe arrecare un danno materiale o psicologico agli interessati stessi - possono rientrare in questa ipotesi, ad esempio, gli studi epidemiologici sulla distribuzione di un fattore che predica o possa predire lo sviluppo di uno stato morboso-)

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Sebbene sia stato svolto ogni ragionevole sforzo organizzativo*, non è possibile contattare gli interessati in ragione: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ del numero molto alto di interessati che è stato stimato ○ perché ci sarebbero conseguenze significative per lo studio in termini di alterazione dei risultati ○ del fatto che i soggetti sono deceduti o persi al follow up <p>* (Motivi di impossibilità organizzativa sono riconducibili alla circostanza che la mancata considerazione dei dati riferiti al numero stimato di interessati che non è possibile contattare per informarli, rispetto al numero complessivo dei soggetti che si intende coinvolgere nella ricerca, produrrebbe conseguenze significative per lo studio in termini di alterazione dei relativi risultati; ciò avuto riguardo, in particolare, ai criteri di inclusione previsti dallo studio, alle modalità di arruolamento, alla numerosità statistica del campione prescelto, nonché al periodo di tempo trascorso dal momento in cui i dati riferiti agli interessati sono stati originariamente raccolti - ad esempio, nei casi in cui lo studio riguarda interessati con patologie ad elevata incidenza di mortalità o in fase terminale della malattia o in età avanzata e in gravi condizioni di salute)</p>
<p>31. Nel caso in cui i partecipanti non abbiano ricevuto l'informativa prima dell'inizio della ricerca, indicare le ragioni per le quali si è reso necessario differire o non fornire l'informativa</p>	<p><input type="checkbox"/> L'informativa è differita perché ci sarebbero conseguenze significative per lo studio in termini di alterazione dei risultati</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Rendere l'informativa comporta un impiego di mezzi manifestamente sproporzionato perché <i>[Indicare le motivazioni per le quali si è ritenuto di differire l'informativa e quali saranno le modalità adottate per informare gli interessati quando saranno venuti meno i motivi che giustificano il differimento, ovvero le ragioni portate per il mancato completamento dell'informativa]:</i></p> <hr/> <hr/> <hr/>
<p>32. Nel caso di trattamenti di dati raccolti presso terzi (es: altri enti o aziende) per altri scopi, indicare le forme di pubblicità adottate nel caso in cui fornire l'informativa singolarmente agli interessati comporti</p>	<p><input type="checkbox"/> l'inserzione su almeno un quotidiano di larga diffusione nazionale o annuncio presso un'emittente radiotelevisiva a diffusione nazionale, per trattamenti riguardanti insiemi numerosi di soggetti distribuiti sull'intero territorio nazionale</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> l'inserzione su un quotidiano di larga diffusione regionale (o provinciale) o annuncio presso un'emittente radiotelevisiva a diffusione regionale (o provinciale), per trattamenti riguardanti</p>

<p>uno sforzo sproporzionato rispetto al diritto tutelato</p>	<p>insiemi numerosi di soggetti distribuiti su un'area regionale (o provinciale)</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> l'inserzione in strumenti informativi (es. sito web) di cui gli interessati sono normalmente destinatari, per trattamenti riguardanti insiemi di specifiche categorie di soggetti, identificate da particolari caratteristiche demografiche e/o da particolari condizioni formative o occupazionali o analoghe</p>
<p>33. Ove previsto, come verrà acquisito il consenso al trattamento dei dati personali?</p>	<hr/> <hr/> <hr/>
<p>34. Nel caso in cui non si possa fornire l'informativa ai soggetti interessati <u>non</u> in grado di esprimere il consenso, a chi si chiederà il consenso alla partecipazione?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ I dati di minori o di soggetti incapaci di esprimere il consenso saranno utilizzati soltanto, se sarà ottenuto il consenso dei genitori o dell'altro genitore in mancanza di uno di essi o del rappresentante legale, ○ Nei casi di incapacità temporanea, all'atto della riacquisizione delle proprie capacità decisionali, al soggetto sarà richiesto il consenso ○ altro (specificare) <hr/> <hr/>
<p>35. Quali modalità saranno adottate per ricevere espressioni di dubbi e rispondere a richieste di precisazioni da parte dei soggetti nel corso dello studio?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Verrà fornita indicazione dei soggetti a cui poter inviare le richieste. Per qualsiasi informazione e chiarimento sullo studio o per qualsiasi necessità nel corso dello studio, i soggetti partecipanti potranno rivolgersi al dottor/professor _____ che è a disposizione per ogni domanda o dubbio ○ Tramite moduli che sono stati predisposti per raccogliere i reclami/segnalazioni e suggerimenti ○ Altro (specificare) <hr/> <hr/>

<p><i>[Da compilare nel caso in cui siano acquisiti dati inerenti lo stato di salute]</i></p> <p>36. In che modo i partecipanti saranno informati della possibilità di ricevere, direttamente o indirettamente, ogni altro dato relativo alle loro condizioni psico-fisiche che dovesse diventare disponibile durante la ricerca?</p>	<p>I partecipanti saranno edotti di tale possibilità nell'informativa. Nel caso in cui dovesse acconsentire alla conoscenza di risultati o notizie inattese, l'interessato potrà ricevere le comunicazioni a mezzo:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="radio"/> Posta <input type="radio"/> Fax <input type="radio"/> Telefono <input type="radio"/> Posta elettronica <input type="radio"/> Medico curante <input type="radio"/> Altro (specificare) <p>_____</p> <p>_____</p>
Valutazione e gestione del rischio, misure di sicurezza e periodo di conservazione	
<p>37. Verranno conservati i dati identificativi dei partecipanti?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="radio"/> NO <input type="radio"/> SI <p>Se sì, specificare le ragioni sottese a tale esigenza</p>
<p>38. Individuazione di misure che contribuiscono alla proporzionalità e alla necessità dell'elaborazione dei dati</p>	<p>Misure previste:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="radio"/> rigorosa limitazione delle quantità di dati raccolti <input type="radio"/> immediata cancellazione dei dati identificativi dopo il loro utilizzo <input type="radio"/> utilizzo di tecniche di anonimizzazione <input type="radio"/> pseudonimizzazione e cifratura di dati personali in fase di conservazione o di transito <input type="radio"/> altro (specificare)
<p>39. Descrivere le procedure utilizzate per non identificare direttamente o rendere anonimi i dati dei partecipanti nelle diverse fasi della ricerca</p>	<p>Per non identificare direttamente l'interessato sono adottate le seguenti misure:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="radio"/> Adozione di tecniche crittografiche <input type="radio"/> Utilizzo di codici univoci per ciascun partecipante. Solo il responsabile della ricerca o altri soggetti autorizzati, possono (con l'uso di mezzi ragionevoli, quali per es. la scheda di progetto) collegare i codici all'identità dei partecipanti <input type="radio"/> Il trattamento dei dati avverrà tramite l'uso di un codice che sarà consegnato ai partecipanti in modo casuale all'inizio dell'esperimento <input type="radio"/> Il trattamento dei dati avverrà tramite l'uso di un codice che sarà scelto dai partecipanti <input type="radio"/> Altro (specificare)

	<p>Per anonimizzare o aggregare i dati, anche in un momento successivo alla raccolta, sono adottate le seguenti misure:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ I dati personali, a seguito della raccolta sono eliminati definitivamente senza la possibilità di risalire ai dati originali ○ I dati personali sono sostituiti da uno o più identificatori, che possono essere utilizzati per un set di dati o per ogni singolo dato ○ Sono distrutti i dati che possono essere idonei a identificare gli interessati e sono conservati i soli dati aggregati ○ Altro (specificare)
<p>40. Per quanto tempo i dati raccolti verranno conservati dalla conclusione della ricerca?</p>	<p>I dati saranno conservati per _____</p> <p>Al termine di questo periodo i dati saranno:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ distrutti ○ conservati in forma anonima
<p>41. Indicare le modalità di conservazione dei dati</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ In formato cartaceo ○ In formato digitale ○ Altro (specificare)
<p>42. Indicare le modalità di conservazione dei dati</p>	<p>Identificare i beni e gli strumenti tramite i quali sono elaborati e/o archiviati i dati personali (hardware, software, reti, persone, canali di trasmissione cartacea, ecc.) nonché descrivere le misure di protezione adottate.</p> <p>_____</p> <p>_____</p> <p>_____</p> <p>_____</p> <p>_____</p>

Luogo

Data

Firma del Responsabile scientifico del progetto

Appendix 5

Dichiarazione di impegno

Con la presente dichiarazione mi impegno a conformarmi alle “Regole deontologiche per trattamenti a fini statistici o di ricerca scientifica” contenute nell’allegato A.4 del codice in materia di protezione dei dati personali (d.lgs. 196/2003) e al rispetto delle norme in materia di protezione dei dati.

Data

Firma

[La dichiarazione è sottoscritta anche dal titolare del progetto e dai soggetti -ricercatori, responsabili e persone autorizzate al trattamento- che sono coinvolti nel prosieguo della ricerca].

Appendix 6

General privacy policy and informed consent forms for fieldwork – ENGLISH

CIRCE Project PRIVACY POLICY

Title of the research project	ERASMUS+ Project <i>Counteracting accent discrimination pRactiCes in Education (CIRCE)</i> AGREEMENT NUMBER: 2022-1-IT02-KA220-SCH-000087602
Scientific Coordinator	Prof. Silvia Calamai (Siena University, Italy) <add name for your institution>

I. GENERAL INFORMATION

You are invited to participate in the CIRCE project (Counteracting accent Discrimination Practices in Education), dedicated to investigating linguistic discrimination in educational contexts, a very important yet still little-known phenomenon. This project aims to:

- i) investigate, within the Italian school population, the social evaluation associated with non-native accents (in English) and/or various local, regional, and standard pronunciations of the Italian language, through responses to dedicated questionnaires.

- ii) collect anonymous autobiographies and linguistic profiles.

The study is conducted at the Department of Philology and Critical Studies of Ancient and Modern Literatures at the University of Siena, in collaboration with the following partners:

- CNR - Institute of Computational Linguistics "Antonio Zampolli" (ILC), Pisa
- WESTFAELISCHE WILHELMS-UNIVERSITAET MUENSTER (UM, Germany);
- UNIVERSITAET HAMBURG (UH, Germany);
- VISOKOSKOLSKA USTANOVA INTERNACIONALNI BURC UNIVERZITET – INTERNATIONAL BURCH UNIVERSITY (IBU, Bosnia and Herzegovina);
- UNIVERSIDADE DE EVORA (UE, Portugal).

The University, as a research centre and as joint-controller, undertakes to process the data concerning you, including "special categories of data" indicated in Article 9 of EU Regulation 2016/679 (such as, for example, personal data relating to health, racial or ethnic origin, political opinions, trade union membership, biometric data) in accordance with the principles established in Article 5 (lawfulness, fairness, transparency, appropriateness, relevance, accuracy, minimisation of processing, limitation of storage, etc.).

The University invites you to read the following notice drafted in agreement with Articles 13 and 14 of the EU Regulation 2016/679 "on the protection of individuals with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data" (hereinafter "Regulation"), also known by the acronym GDPR (General Data Protection Regulation).

II. JOINT DATA CONTROLLERS

Under the terms of the related joint-controller agreement, the Data Controllers are:

Università degli Studi di Siena

with headquarters in Banchi di Sotto 55, 53100 Siena – Italy
represented by Prof. Dr. **, Legal Representative, Rector
Email: rettore@unisi.it
Certified Email (PEC): rettore@pec.unisipec.it

Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche

with headquarters in Piazzale Aldo Moro 7, 00185 Roma – Italy
represented by Dr. **, Legal Representative, Director of the Istituto di Linguistica Computazionale "Antonio Zampolli" of the Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche, with headquarters in the Area della Ricerca del CNR di Pisa, Via Giuseppe Moruzzi 1, 56124 Pisa ITALY
Email: direttore@ilc.cnr.it
Certified Email (PEC): protocollo.ilc@pec.cnr.it

Universitaet Hamburg

with headquarters in Mittelweg 177 20148 Hamburg – Germany
represented by Prof. Dr. **, Legal Representative, President of Universitaet Hamburg
Email: praesident@uni-hamburg.de

Westfaelische Wilhelms-Universitaet Muenster

with headquarters in Schlossplatz 2, 48149 Muenster – Germany
represented by Prof. Dr. **, Legal Representative
Email: **@uni-muenster.de

Universidade de Évora

with headquarters in Largo dos Colegiais, 2 7000-803 Évora – Portugal

represented by Prof. Dr. **, Legal Representative, Vice-Rector
Email: investigar@scs.uevora.pt

The essential content of the joint-controller agreement will be made available to the data subject upon their request via email at gdpr.circe@unisi.it.

III. DATA PROTECTION OFFICERS

The Data Protection Officers of the joint Data Controllers are:

Università degli Studi di Siena

DPO: Dr. **

Email: rpd@unisi.it

Certified Email (PEC): rpd@pec.unisipec.it

Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche

Email: rpd@cnr.it

Certified Email (PEC): rpd@pec.cnr.it

Universitaet Hamburg

DPO: **

Email: datenschutz@uni-hamburg.de

Westfaelische Wilhelms-Universitaet Muenster

DPO: **

Email: datenschutz@uni-muenster.de

Universidade de Évora

DPO: **

Email: epd@uevora.pt

IV. PURPOSES AND MEANS OF DATA PROCESSING

a) The processing purposes of your personal data are as follows:

- carrying out the "CIRCE" research project and achieving its objectives as described in Section I;
- dissemination of the results of the "CIRCE" project;
- administrative management of the project.

b) Your personal data, especially those belonging to special categories (Article 9 GDPR), will be collected and processed with appropriate levels of security, specifically:

- in a way that allows your identification only when strictly necessary;
- in paper or electronic form, feeding paper and/or electronic archives for research-related needs;
- exclusively within premises and systems (hardware and software) that are protected and compliant with security measures prescribed by regulations and security standards.

c) Considering that new discoveries may indicate fresh research opportunities for researchers or enable further studies and investigations on the data provided by you, your personal data may be processed for additional research purposes, in accordance with applicable regulations. Additionally, the Scientific Coordinator of the ongoing project may contact you to seek your new, specific consent (should you deem it appropriate) for further research on your data.

The categories of personal data processed include:

- oral and audio-visual data (audio and video interviews, short life stories, podcasts), which may include special categories of personal data under Article 9 of EU Regulation 2016/679;
- written linguistic autobiographies, which may include special categories of personal data;

- behavioural data, such as reaction times and responses to auditory stimuli, which may be processed for statistical analysis.

For the processing of images, specific consent from the data subject is required, in accordance with copyright law provisions.

V. LEGAL BASIS

The processing of your personal data by the University will be carried out on the basis of at least one of the following legal grounds for processing, or "lawful bases for processing":

- explicit consent provided by the data subject for one or more processing purposes as outlined in Section IV of this policy.
- pursuit of a legitimate interest, which consists in the execution and development of the CIRCE project and is therefore related to the achievement of the purposes described in Section IV of this policy.

The processing of personal data belonging to "special categories" (formerly known as "sensitive data") will be carried out on the basis of at least one of the following legal grounds for processing:

- explicit consent of the data subject for one or more of the purposes indicated in Section IV of this policy.
- necessity to establish, exercise, or defend a legal claim in a judicial proceeding.
- archiving in the public interest, for scientific or historical research, or statistical purposes.

VI. INTERNAL RECIPIENTS OF DATA

The recipients of your personal data are partners of the project which are joint-controllers and that are listed in Section II. The research units and the collaborators in research activities of each partner (researchers, technicians, and administrative staff) may access data. They will process these data, both through automated and non-automated means, exclusively to facilitate the execution of the research and all related operations and activities, including administrative tasks.

VII. ENTITIES DIFFERENT FROM THE JOINT CONTROLLERS WITH WHOM DATA MAY BE SHARED AND TRANSFER OF PERSONAL DATA TO THIRD COUNTRIES OR INTERNATIONAL ORGANIZATIONS

The collected data may be shared for the purposes outlined in Section IV, including the sharing of research activities and subsequent dissemination of results with the project partner INTERNACIONALNI BURČ UNIVERZITET-INTERNATIONAL BURCH UNIVERSITY (IBU, Bosnia and Herzegovina). The transfer to Bosnia, and thus outside the European Economic Area, will only be carried out after the adoption of standard data protection clauses approved by the European Commission through Implementing Decision (EU) 2021/914 of June 4, 2021, and following statements from the Bosnian partner ensuring the adequacy of the level of protection guaranteed by the national legislation applicable to the processing of personal data.

The collected data may also be shared, again for the purposes outlined in Section IV, with the Zenodo repository (<https://zenodo.org/>), operated by CERN (Switzerland) on behalf of OpenAIRE (EU). This transfer is carried out in compliance with EU Reg. 2016/679, including Art. 45 thereof, and on the basis of the Commission Decision of 26 July 2000 pursuant to Directive 95/46/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council on the adequate protection of personal data provided in Switzerland (notified under document number C(2000) 2304).

All the documentation collected during the research may be reviewed by Committees of Italian and foreign scientific journals and international organizations to ensure that the research is conducted correctly and in accordance with applicable regulations. In any case, data transfers will respect applicable legislation, including Reg. UE 2016/679.

VIII. DATA SUBJECT RIGHTS

In their capacity as a data subject, the research participant has the right to exercise all the rights provided for in Articles 15 and following of the European Regulation. In particular, they can obtain:

- access to their personal data and all other information indicated in Article 15;
- rectification of data if they are inaccurate and/or their completion if they are incomplete;
- erasure (the so-called "right to be forgotten"), except for information that must be retained for the purposes outlined in Section IV and unless there is a prevailing legitimate reason for continuing data processing;
- restriction of processing in cases specified in Article 18;
- object to processing (in cases provided for by regulations);
- data portability (in cases provided for by regulations).

According to the provisions of the European Regulation, data subjects also have the right to:

- withdraw consent at any time without affecting the lawfulness of processing based on consent before its withdrawal;
- lodge a complaint with a supervisory authority.

IX. EXERCISE OF RIGHTS AND COMPLAINT TO THE DATA PROTECTION AUTHORITY

If the data subject wishes to exercise the rights described above, they may contact the Data Controller using the contact information provided in Section II of this notice.

For reporting any violations of personal data processing rules or to report data breaches (where a data breach refers to a security incident that results in the accidental or unlawful destruction, loss, alteration, unauthorized disclosure, or access to personal data transmitted, stored, or otherwise processed), the data subject can also use the dedicated data breach reporting service activated by the University of Siena, reachable at the following addresses: rpd.breach@pec.unisipec.it; abuse@unisi.it. The data breach reporting service operates under the authority and direct control of the Data Controller.

A response to the request will be provided as soon as possible. According to the Regulation, a response should be given within one month of the request, which can be extended to three months in cases of particular complexity.

The data subject also has the right to lodge a complaint with the supervisory authority as provided in Article 77 of the Regulation. In Italy, the supervisory authority is represented by the Garante per la Protezione dei dati personali (<https://www.garanteprivacy.it>).

X. DATA RETENTION PERIOD

The data collected during the research will be recorded, processed, and stored for the duration necessary for the completion of the CIRCE project as described in Section I. Furthermore, the data may be further retained and processed in accordance with Article 89 of the EU Regulation, that is ensuring adequate safeguards to protect the rights and freedoms of the data subject, and in compliance with Article 99 of Legislative Decree 196/2003 and other regulations concerning data processing for the purposes of public interest archiving, scientific or historical research, and statistical purposes.

In particular, the management and storage of personal data collected for research purposes in Italy are carried out by the University of Siena, including any data processors appointed by the University to ensure its operation and services, and by CNR-ILC. Details of the data storage methods can be found in the *Data Management Plan*, accessible from the dedicated section of the CIRCE website (<https://www.circe-project.eu>).

XI. NATURE OF DATA PROVISION AND CONSEQUENCES OF REFUSAL TO PROVIDE

The provision of data for the purposes described in Section IV, letter a), is essential for the conduct of the study and is not a legal obligation. Refusal to provide these data will prevent the data subject from participating in the study in question.

The provision of data for the purposes described in Section IV, letters b) and c), is optional, not required by law, and is intended to facilitate the retention of data for a longer period than that envisaged for the conclusion of the present study, potentially allowing the Data Controller, through the Scientific Coordinator of the ongoing project, to contact you for the purpose of obtaining new, specific consent (should you deem it appropriate) for further research.

Consent form for Verbal Guise Test participants (minors and adults)

CONSENT FORM

Subject: Participation in the CIRCE Project

The participant is a minor

Parent/Guardian legal name: _____

Place of birth: _____ (_____)

Date of birth: ____/____/____

Legal address: _____

Participant legal name: _____

The participant is an adult

Participant legal name: _____

Place of birth: _____ (_____)

Date of birth: ____/____/____

Legal address: _____

I express my consent to the participation in the project in question and I hereby authorize the university staff working within the CIRCE project (researchers, research collaborators) to:

- carrying out perceptual investigations by means of experimental tests (in paper and/or digital form);
- carry out surveys by means of a sociolinguistic questionnaire (in paper and/or digital form);
- use the above-mentioned contents both in their entirety and partially, for the purposes of sociolinguistic research, including publications and research reports as well as quotations during lectures, seminars and conferences and statistical analyses;
- disseminate and reproduce the above-mentioned contents, both in paper and digital form in the ways that the University will deem appropriate.

I hereby declare that:

- I have been adequately informed about the aims of the project and the way in which my/my son's/my daughter's/my ward's contribution may be used;
- I have nothing to claim from the University of Siena regarding the use of the material collected as indicated above, either now or in the future;

- the copyright of the data obtained through experiments and/or surveys is the total property of the University of Siena, which owns all the rights of reproduction, publication and dissemination according to the uses permitted by law.

Date _____

Signature _____

PROCESSING OF PERSONAL DATA

You are invited to read the detailed Privacy Policy drafted according to EU Regulation 2016/679, which is delivered to you together with this form, and you are informed that:

- Your/your son's/your daughter's/your ward's data will be processed in accordance with the principles established in Article 5 (lawfulness, correctness, transparency, appropriateness, relevance, accuracy, minimisation of processing, limitation of storage, etc.); under the terms of the related joint-controller agreement, the Data Controllers are:
 - **The Università degli Studi di Siena**, with headquarters in Banchi di Sotto 55, 53100 Siena – Italy, represented by, Prof. Dr. **, Legal Representative, Rector;
 - **The Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche**, with headquarters in Piazzale Aldo Moro 7, 00185 Roma – Italy, represented by Dr. **, Legal Representative, Director of the Istituto di Linguistica Computazionale “Antonio Zampolli” of the Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche, with headquarters in the Area della Ricerca del CNR di Pisa, Via Giuseppe Moruzzi 1, 56124 Pisa ITALY;
 - **The Universitaet Hamburg**, with headquarters in Mittelweg 177 20148 Hamburg – Germany, represented by Prof. Dr. **, Legal Representative President of Universität Hamburg;
 - **The Westfaelische Wilhelms-Universitaet Muenster**, with headquarters in Schlossplatz 2, 48149 Muenster – Germany, represented by Dr. **;
 - **The Universidade de Évora**, with headquarters in Largo dos Colegiais, 2 7000-803 Évora – Portugal, represented by Prof. Dr. **, Legal Representative, Vice-Rector.
- The Data Protection Officers (DPO) of the joint Data Controllers are:
 - **Università degli Studi di Siena**
DPO: Dr. **
Email: rpd@unisi.it
Certified Email (PEC): rpd@pec.unisipec.it
 - **Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche**
Email: rpd@cnr.it
Certified Email (PEC): rpd@pec.cnr.it
 - **Universitaet Hamburg**
DPO: **
Email: datenschutz@uni-hamburg.de
 - **Westfaelische Wilhelms-Universitaet Muenster**
DPO: **
Email: datenschutz@uni-muenster.de
 - **Universidade de Évora**
DPO: **
Email: epd@uevora.pt

- The data will be acquired for the purposes of the University of Siena's sociolinguistic research, including publications and research reports as well as quotations during lectures, seminars and conferences, for sociolinguistic analyses; to carry out institutional communications (including interactive ones). They will be collected and processed with the aid of paper and computer instruments in such a way as to guarantee security and confidentiality, feeding paper and/or computer archives;
- As a data subject, you may exercise against the University of Siena all the rights envisaged by Articles 15 et seq. of the European Regulation; in particular, you may obtain: access to your/your son's/your daughter's/your ward's personal data, their rectification or integration, their deletion (so-called "right to be forgotten"), the restriction of processing;
- Giving consent to the processing of your/your son's/your daughter's/your ward's personal data is optional. In the absence of your consent, you will not be able to participate in the CIRCE project of which the University of Siena is the lead partner, in a partnership consisting of:
 CNR - Institute of Computational Linguistics "Antonio Zampolli" (ILC, Pisa);
 WESTFAELISCHE WILHELMS-UNIVERSITAET MUENSTER (UM, Germany);
 UNIVERSITAET HAMBURG (UH, Germany);
 UNIVERSIDADE DE EVORA (EU, Portugal);
 VISOKOSKOLSKA USTANOVA INTERNACIONALNI BURC UNIVERZITET – INTERNATIONAL BURCH UNIVERSITY (IBU, Bosnia and Herzegovina).

The undersigned _____

having carefully read the information notice on the processing of their/their son's/their daughter's/their ward's personal data

consents to the processing of their/their son's/their daughter's/their ward's personal data for all the purposes specified in Title IV of the privacy policy

does not consent to the processing of their/their son's/their daughter's/their ward's personal data

Date _____

Signature _____

Privacy policy and consent form for podcast

CIRCE Project PRIVACY POLICY	
Project Title	Progetto ERASMUS+ <i>Counteracting accent discrimination pRactiCes in Education (CIRCE)</i> AGREEMENT NUMBER: 2022-1-IT02-KA220-SCH-000087602
Scientific Coordinator	Prof. Silvia Calamai (Siena University, Italy) <add name for your institution>
I. GENERAL INFORMATION	

You are invited to take part in a study that aims at the collection of audio/video recordings to be published as podcasts with the objective of investigating, within the Italian school and university population, the social evaluation associated with non-native English accents and/or the different local, regional and standard pronunciations of the Italian language. The audio and audio-video podcasts collected may be published on the CIRCE website and social channels and may be deposited in online archives accessible on request. Specifically, the podcasts will be deposited on Zenodo (the open access archive for researchers' publications and data managed by CERN on behalf of OpenAIRE (EU)) and on ILC4CLARIN (the data centre of the CLARIN-IT infrastructure, the Italian component of the European federation of CLARIN).

The study is being conducted by personnel belonging to the Department of Philology and Literary Criticism, in collaboration with the following partners:

CNR - Institute of Computational Linguistics 'Antonio Zampolli' (ILC, Pisa);

WESTFAELISCHE WILHELMS-UNIVERSITAET MUENSTER (UM, Germany);

UNIVERSITAET HAMBURG (UH, Germany);

UNIVERSIDADE DE EVORA (EU, Portugal);

VISOKOSKOLSKA USTANOVA INTERNACIONALNI BURC UNIVERZITET-INTERNATIONAL BURCH UNIVERSITY (IBU, Bosnia and Herzegovina).

The University, as a research centre and as joint-controller, undertakes to process the data concerning you, including "special categories of data" indicated in Article 9 of EU Regulation 2016/679 (such as, for example, personal data relating to health, racial or ethnic origin, political opinions, trade union membership, biometric data) in accordance with the principles established in Article 5 (lawfulness, fairness, transparency, appropriateness, relevance, accuracy, minimisation of processing, limitation of storage, etc.).

The University invites you to read the following notice drafted in agreement with Articles 13 and 14 of the EU Regulation 2016/679 "on the protection of individuals with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data" (hereinafter "Regulation"), also known by the acronym GDPR (General Data Protection Regulation).

II. JOINT DATA CONTROLLERS

Under the terms of the related joint-controller agreement, the Data Controllers are:

Università degli Studi di Siena

with headquarters in Banchi di Sotto 55, 53100 Siena – Italy

represented by Prof. Dr. **, Legal Representative, Rector

Email: rettore@unisi.it Certified Email (PEC): rettore@pec.unisipec.it

Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche

with headquarters in Piazzale Aldo Moro 7, 00185 Roma – Italy

represented by Dr. Simonetta Montemagni, Legal Representative, Director of the Istituto di Linguistica Computazionale "Antonio Zampolli" of the Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche, with headquarters in the Area della Ricerca del CNR di Pisa, Via Giuseppe Moruzzi 1, 56124 Pisa ITALY

Email: direttore@ilc.cnr.it Certified Email (PEC): protocollo.ilc@pec.cnr.it

Universitaet Hamburg

with headquarters in Mittelweg 177 20148 Hamburg – Germany

represented by Prof. Dr. Hauke Heekeren, Legal Representative, President of Universitaet Hamburg

Email: praesident@uni-hamburg.de

Westfaelische Wilhelms-Universitaet Muenster

with headquarters in Schlossplatz 2, 48149 Muenster – Germany
represented by Dr. Katharina Steinberg, Legal Representative
Email: katharina.steinberg@uni-muenster.de

Universidade de Évora

with headquarters in Largo dos Colegiais, 2 7000-803 Évora – Portugal
represented by Prof. Dr. Paulo Quaresma, Legal Representative, Vice-Rector
Email: investigar@scc.uevora.pt

The essential content of the joint-controller agreement will be made available to the data subject upon their request via email at gdpr.circe@unisi.it.

III. DATA PROTECTION OFFICERS

The Data Protection Officers of the joint Data Controllers are:

Università degli Studi di Siena

DPO: Dr. Chiara Silvia Armida Angiolini
Email: rpd@unisi.it
Certified Email (PEC): rpd@pec.unisipec.it

Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche

Email: rpd@cnr.it
Certified Email (PEC): rpd@pec.cnr.it

Universitaet Hamburg

DPO: Corinna Diercks
Email: datenschutz@uni-hamburg.de

Westfaelische Wilhelms-Universitaet Muenster

DPO: Nina Meyer-Pachur
Email: datenschutz@uni-muenster.de

Universidade de Évora

DPO: Prof. João Vaz Rodrigues
Email: epd@uevora.pt

IV. PURPOSES AND MEANS OF DATA PROCESSING

a) The processing purposes of your personal data are as follows:

- carrying out the "CIRCE" research project and achieving its objectives as described in Section I;
- dissemination of the results of the "CIRCE" project;
- administrative management of the project.

b) Your personal data, especially those belonging to special categories (Article 9 GDPR), will be collected and processed with appropriate levels of security, specifically:

- in a way that allows your identification only when strictly necessary;
- in paper or electronic form, feeding paper and/or electronic archives for research-related needs;
- exclusively within premises and systems (hardware and software) that are protected and compliant with security measures prescribed by regulations and security standards.

c) Considering that new discoveries may indicate fresh research opportunities for researchers or enable further studies and investigations on the data provided by you, your personal data may be processed for additional research purposes, in accordance with applicable regulations. Additionally, the Scientific Coordinator of the ongoing project may contact you to seek your new, specific consent (should you deem it appropriate) for further research on your data.

V. LEGAL BASIS

The processing of your personal data by the University will be carried out on the basis of at least one of the following legal grounds for processing, or "lawful bases for processing":

- explicit consent provided by the data subject for one or more processing purposes as outlined in Section IV of this policy.
- pursuit of a legitimate interest, which consists in the execution and development of the CIRCE project and is therefore related to the achievement of the purposes described in Section IV of this policy.

The processing of personal data belonging to "special categories" (formerly known as "sensitive data") will be carried out on the basis of at least one of the following legal grounds for processing:

- explicit consent of the data subject for one or more of the purposes indicated in Section IV of this policy.
- necessity to establish, exercise, or defend a legal claim in a judicial proceeding.
- archiving in the public interest, for scientific or historical research, or statistical purposes.

VI. INTERNAL RECIPIENTS OF DATA

The recipients of your personal data are partners of the project which are joint-controllers and that are listed in Section II. The research units and the collaborators in research activities of each partner (researchers, technicians, and administrative staff) may access data. They will process these data, both through automated and non-automated means, exclusively to facilitate the execution of the research and all related operations and activities, including administrative tasks.

VII. ENTITIES DIFFERENT FROM THE JOINT CONTROLLERS WITH WHOM DATA MAY BE SHARED AND TRANSFER OF PERSONAL DATA TO THIRD COUNTRIES OR INTERNATIONAL ORGANIZATIONS

The collected data may be shared for the purposes outlined in Section IV, including the sharing of research activities and subsequent dissemination of results with the project partner INTERNACIONALNI BURČ UNIVERZITET-INTERNATIONAL BURCH UNIVERSITY (IBU, Bosnia and Herzegovina). The transfer to Bosnia, and thus outside the European Economic Area, will only be carried out after the adoption of standard data protection clauses approved by the European Commission through Implementing Decision (EU) 2021/914 of June 4, 2021, and following statements from the Bosnian partner ensuring the adequacy of the level of protection guaranteed by the national legislation applicable to the processing of personal data.

The collected data may also be shared, again for the purposes outlined in Section IV, with the Zenodo repository (<https://zenodo.org/>), operated by CERN (Switzerland) on behalf of OpenAIRE (EU). This transfer is carried out in compliance with EU Reg. 2016/679, including Art. 45 thereof, and on the basis of the Commission Decision of 26 July 2000 pursuant to Directive 95/46/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council on the adequate protection of personal data provided in Switzerland (notified under document number C(2000) 2304).

All the documentation collected during the research may be reviewed by Committees of Italian and foreign scientific journals and international organizations to ensure that the research is conducted correctly and in accordance with applicable regulations. In any case, data transfers will respect applicable legislation, including Reg. UE 2016/679.

VIII. DATA SUBJECT RIGHTS

In their capacity as a data subject, the research participant has the right to exercise all the rights provided for in Articles 15 and following of the European Regulation. In particular, they can obtain:

- access to their personal data and all other information indicated in Article 15;
- rectification of data if they are inaccurate and/or their completion if they are incomplete;
- erasure (the so-called "right to be forgotten"), except for information that must be retained for the purposes outlined in Section IV and unless there is a prevailing legitimate reason for continuing data processing;
- restriction of processing in cases specified in Article 18;
- object to processing (in cases provided for by regulations);
- data portability (in cases provided for by regulations).

According to the provisions of the European Regulation, data subjects also have the right to:

- withdraw consent at any time without affecting the lawfulness of processing based on consent before its withdrawal;
- lodge a complaint with a supervisory authority.

IX. EXERCISE OF RIGHTS AND COMPLAINT TO THE DATA PROTECTION AUTHORITY

If the data subject wishes to exercise the rights described above, they may contact the Data Controller using the contact information provided in Section II of this notice.

For reporting any violations of personal data processing rules or to report data breaches (where a data breach refers to a security incident that results in the accidental or unlawful destruction, loss, alteration, unauthorized disclosure, or access to personal data transmitted, stored, or otherwise processed), the data subject can also use the dedicated data breach reporting service activated by the University of Siena, reachable at the following addresses: rp.d.breach@pec.unisipecc.it; abuse@unisi.it. The data breach reporting service operates under the authority and direct control of the Data Controller. A response to the request will be provided as soon as possible. According to the Regulation, a response should be given within one month of the request, which can be extended to three months in cases of particular complexity.

The data subject also has the right to lodge a complaint with the supervisory authority as provided in Article 77 of the Regulation. In Italy, the supervisory authority is represented by the Garante per la Protezione dei dati personali (<https://www.garanteprivacy.it>).

X. DATA RETENTION PERIOD

The data collected during the research will be recorded, processed, and stored for the duration necessary for the completion of the CIRCE project as described in Section I. Furthermore, the data may be further retained and processed in accordance with Article 89 of the EU Regulation, that is ensuring adequate safeguards to protect the rights and freedoms of the data subject, and in compliance with Article 99 of Legislative Decree 196/2003 and other regulations concerning data processing for the purposes of public interest archiving, scientific or historical research, and statistical purposes.

In particular, the management and storage of personal data collected for research purposes in Italy are carried out by the University of Siena, including any data processors appointed by the University to ensure

its operation and services, and by CNR-ILC. Details of the data storage methods can be found in the *Data Management Plan*, accessible from the dedicated section of the CIRCE website (<https://www.circe-project.eu>).

XI. NATURE OF DATA PROVISION AND CONSEQUENCES OF REFUSAL TO PROVIDE

The provision of data for the purposes described in Section IV, letter a), is essential for the conduct of the study and is not a legal obligation. Refusal to provide these data will prevent the data subject from participating in the study in question.

The provision of data for the purposes described in Section IV, letters b) and c), is optional, not required by law, and is intended to facilitate the retention of data for a longer period than that envisaged for the conclusion of the present study, potentially allowing the Data Controller, through the Scientific Coordinator of the ongoing project, to contact you for the purpose of obtaining new, specific consent (should you deem it appropriate) for further research.

CONSENT FORM

Subject: Collection of audio-video podcast as part of the CIRCE Project

Legal name _____

Place of birth: _____ (_____)

Date of birth: ____/____/____

Legal address: _____

I express my consent to participate in the project in question and I hereby authorize the university staff working within the CIRCE project (researchers, research collaborators) to:

- use the podcasts content both in its entirety and partially, for the purposes of sociolinguistic research, including publications and research reports as well as quotations during lectures, seminars and conferences and statistical analyses;
- disclose and reproduce the audio-video documentation, both in paper and digital form in the ways that the University will deem appropriate.

I hereby declare that:

- I have been adequately informed about the aims of the project and the way in which my contribution may be used;
- I have nothing to claim from the University of Siena regarding the use of the material collected as indicated above, either now or in the future;
- the copyright of the data obtained through registration is the total property of the University of Siena, which owns all the rights of reproduction, publication and dissemination according to the uses permitted by law.

Date _____

Signature _____

PROCESSING OF PERSONAL DATA

You are invited to read the detailed Privacy Policy drafted according to EU Regulation 2016/679, which is delivered to you together with this form, and you are informed that:

- Your data will be processed in accordance with the principles established in Article 5 (lawfulness, correctness, transparency, appropriateness, relevance, accuracy, minimisation of processing, limitation of storage, etc.); under the terms of the related joint-controller agreement, the Data Controllers are:
 - **The Università degli Studi di Siena**, with headquarters in Banchi di Sotto 55, 53100 Siena – Italy, represented by, Prof. Dr. **, Legal Representative, Rector;
 - **The Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche**, with headquarters in Piazzale Aldo Moro 7, 00185 Roma – Italy, represented by Dr. **, Legal Representative, Director of the Istituto di Linguistica Computazionale “Antonio Zampolli” of the Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche, with headquarters in the Area della Ricerca del CNR di Pisa, Via Giuseppe Moruzzi 1, 56124 Pisa ITALY;
 - **The Universitaet Hamburg**, with headquarters in Mittelweg 177 20148 Hamburg – Germany, represented by Prof. Dr. **, Legal Representative President of Universität Hamburg;
 - **The Westfaelische Wilhelms-Universitaet Muenster**, with headquarters in Schlossplatz 2, 48149 Muenster – Germany, represented by Dr. **;
 - **The Universidade de Évora**, with headquarters in Largo dos Colegiais, 2 7000-803 Évora – Portugal, represented by Prof. Dr. **, Legal Representative, Vice-Rector.

- The Data Protection Officers (DPO) of the joint Data Controllers are:
 - **Università degli Studi di Siena**
DPO: Dr. **
Email: rpd@unisi.it
Certified Email (PEC): rpd@pec.unisipec.it
 - **Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche**
Email: rpd@cnr.it
Certified Email (PEC): rpd@pec.cnr.it
 - **Universitaet Hamburg**
DPO: **
Email: datenschutz@uni-hamburg.de
 - **Westfaelische Wilhelms-Universitaet Muenster**
DPO: **
Email: datenschutz@uni-muenster.de
 - **Universidade de Évora**
DPO: Prof. **
Email: epd@uevora.pt

- The data will be acquired for the purposes of the University of Siena's sociolinguistic research, including publications and research reports as well as quotations during lectures, seminars and conferences, for sociolinguistic analyses; to carry out institutional communications (including interactive ones). They will be collected and processed with the aid of paper and computer instruments in such a way as to guarantee security and confidentiality, feeding paper and/or computer archives;

- As a data subject, you may exercise against the University of Siena all the rights envisaged by Articles 15 et seq. of the European Regulation; in particular, you may obtain: access to your personal data, their rectification or integration, their deletion (so-called "right to be forgotten"), the restriction of processing.
- Giving consent to the processing of your personal data is optional. In the absence of your consent, you will not be able to participate in the CIRCE project of which the University of Siena is the lead partner, in a partnership consisting of:
 CNR - Institute of Computational Linguistics "Antonio Zampolli" (ILC, Pisa);
 WESTFAELISCHE WILHELMS-UNIVERSITAET MUENSTER (UM, Germany);
 UNIVERSITAET HAMBURG (UH, Germany);
 UNIVERSIDADE DE EVORA (EU, Portugal);
 VISOKOSKOLSKA USTANOVA INTERNACIONALNI BURC UNIVERZITET – INTERNATIONAL BURCH UNIVERSITY (IBU, Bosnia and Herzegovina).

The undersigned _____

having carefully read the information notice on the processing of their personal data

- consents to the processing of their personal data for all the purposes specified in Title IV of the privacy policy
- does not consent to the processing of their personal data

Date _____

Signature _____

Privacy policy and consent form for Verbal Guise Test voices recording

CIRCE Project PRIVACY POLICY

Project Title	Progetto ERASMUS+ <i>Counteracting accent discrimination pRactiCes in Education (CIRCE)</i> AGREEMENT NUMBER: 2022-1-IT02-KA220-SCH-000087602
Scientific Coordinator	Prof. Silvia Calamai (Siena University, Italy) <add name for your institution>

I. GENERAL INFORMATION

You are invited to take part in a study that aims to collect samples of pseudo-anonymised voices (Italian and non-Italian) with the objective of building a corpus of voices useful to investigate, within the Italian school population, the social evaluation associated with non-native English accents and/or the various local, regional and standard pronunciations of the Italian language.

The collected audio files will be described and collected in a corpus, usable for non-profit research purposes, which will be deposited in online archives accessible only upon request. Specifically, the corpus of voices will be deposited on Zenodo (the open access repository for publications and data by researchers

managed by CERN on behalf of OpenAIRE (EU)) and/or on ILC4CLARIN (the data centre of the CLARIN-IT infrastructure, the Italian component of the European federation of CLARIN).

The study is being conducted by personnel belonging to the Department of Philology and Criticism of Ancient and Modern Literature, in collaboration with the following partners:

CNR - Institute of Computational Linguistics 'Antonio Zampolli' (ILC, Pisa);

WESTFAELISCHE WILHELMS-UNIVERSITAET MUENSTER (UM, Germany);

UNIVERSITAET HAMBURG (UH, Germany);

UNIVERSIDADE DE EVORA (EU, Portugal);

VISOKOSKOLSKA USTANOVA INTERNACIONALNI BURC UNIVERZITET-INTERNATIONAL BURCH UNIVERSITY (IBU, Bosnia and Herzegovina).

The University, as a research centre and as joint-controller, undertakes to process the data concerning you, including "special categories of data" indicated in Article 9 of EU Regulation 2016/679 (such as, for example, personal data relating to health, racial or ethnic origin, political opinions, trade union membership, biometric data) in accordance with the principles established in Article 5 (lawfulness, fairness, transparency, appropriateness, relevance, accuracy, minimisation of processing, limitation of storage, etc.).

The University invites you to read the following notice drafted in agreement with Articles 13 and 14 of the EU Regulation 2016/679 "on the protection of individuals with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data" (hereinafter "Regulation"), also known by the acronym GDPR (General Data Protection Regulation).

II. JOINT DATA CONTROLLERS

Under the terms of the related joint-controller agreement, the Data Controllers are:

Università degli Studi di Siena

with headquarters in Banchi di Sotto 55, 53100 Siena – Italy

represented by Prof. Dr. **, Legal Representative, Rector

Email: rettore@unisi.it Certified Email (PEC): rettore@pec.unisipec.it

Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche

with headquarters in Piazzale Aldo Moro 7, 00185 Roma – Italy

represented by Dr. **, Legal Representative, Director of the Istituto di Linguistica Computazionale "Antonio Zampolli" of the Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche, with headquarters in the Area della Ricerca del CNR di Pisa, Via Giuseppe Moruzzi 1, 56124 Pisa ITALY

Email: direttore@ilc.cnr.it Certified Email (PEC): protocollo.ilc@pec.cnr.it

Universitaet Hamburg

with headquarters in Mittelweg 177 20148 Hamburg – Germany

represented by Prof. Dr. **, Legal Representative, President of Universitaet Hamburg

Email: praesident@uni-hamburg.de

Westfaelische Wilhelms-Universitaet Muenster

with headquarters in Schlossplatz 2, 48149 Muenster – Germany

represented by Dr. **, Legal Representative

Email: katharina.steinberg@uni-muenster.de

Universidade de Évora

with headquarters in Largo dos Colegiais, 2 7000-803 Évora – Portugal

represented by Prof. Dr. **, Legal Representative, Vice-Rector

Email: investigar@scc.uevora.pt

The essential content of the joint-controller agreement will be made available to the data subject upon their request via email at gdpr.circe@unisi.it.

III. DATA PROTECTION OFFICERS

The Data Protection Officers of the joint Data Controllers are:

Università degli Studi di Siena

DPO: Dr. **

Email: rpd@unisi.it

Certified Email (PEC): rpd@pec.unisipec.it

Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche

Email: rpd@cnr.it

Certified Email (PEC): rpd@pec.cnr.it

Universitaet Hamburg

DPO: **

Email: datenschutz@uni-hamburg.de

Westfaelische Wilhelms-Universitaet Muenster

DPO: **

Email: datenschutz@uni-muenster.de

Universidade de Évora

DPO: Prof. **

Email: epd@uevora.pt

IV. PURPOSES AND MEANS OF DATA PROCESSING

a) The processing purposes of your personal data are as follows:

- carrying out the "CIRCE" research project and achieving its objectives as described in Section I;
- dissemination of the results of the "CIRCE" project;
- administrative management of the project.

b) Your personal data, especially those belonging to special categories (Article 9 GDPR), will be collected and processed with appropriate levels of security, specifically:

- in a way that allows your identification only when strictly necessary;
- in paper or electronic form, feeding paper and/or electronic archives for research-related needs;
- exclusively within premises and systems (hardware and software) that are protected and compliant with security measures prescribed by regulations and security standards.

c) Considering that new discoveries may indicate fresh research opportunities for researchers or enable further studies and investigations on the data provided by you, your personal data may be processed for additional research purposes, in accordance with applicable regulations. Additionally, the Scientific Coordinator of the ongoing project may contact you to seek your new, specific consent (should you deem it appropriate) for further research on your data.

V. LEGAL BASIS

The processing of your personal data by the University will be carried out on the basis of at least one of the following legal grounds for processing, or "lawful bases for processing":

- explicit consent provided by the data subject for one or more processing purposes as outlined in Section IV of this policy.

- pursuit of a legitimate interest, which consists in the execution and development of the CIRCE project and is therefore related to the achievement of the purposes described in Section IV of this policy.

The processing of personal data belonging to "special categories" (formerly known as "sensitive data") will be carried out on the basis of at least one of the following legal grounds for processing:

- explicit consent of the data subject for one or more of the purposes indicated in Section IV of this policy.
- necessity to establish, exercise, or defend a legal claim in a judicial proceeding.
- archiving in the public interest, for scientific or historical research, or statistical purposes.

VI. INTERNAL RECIPIENTS OF DATA

The recipients of your personal data are partners of the project which are joint-controllers and that are listed in Section II. The research units and the collaborators in research activities of each partner (researchers, technicians, and administrative staff) may access data. They will process these data, both through automated and non-automated means, exclusively to facilitate the execution of the research and all related operations and activities, including administrative tasks.

VII. ENTITIES DIFFERENT FROM THE JOINT CONTROLLERS WITH WHOM DATA MAY BE SHARED AND TRANSFER OF PERSONAL DATA TO THIRD COUNTRIES OR INTERNATIONAL ORGANIZATIONS

The collected data may be shared for the purposes outlined in Section IV, including the sharing of research activities and subsequent dissemination of results with the project partner INTERNACIONALNI BURČ UNIVERZITET-INTERNATIONAL BURCH UNIVERSITY (IBU, Bosnia and Herzegovina). The transfer to Bosnia, and thus outside the European Economic Area, will only be carried out after the adoption of standard data protection clauses approved by the European Commission through Implementing Decision (EU) 2021/914 of June 4, 2021, and following statements from the Bosnian partner ensuring the adequacy of the level of protection guaranteed by the national legislation applicable to the processing of personal data.

The collected data may also be shared, again for the purposes outlined in Section IV, with the Zenodo repository (<https://zenodo.org/>), operated by CERN (Switzerland) on behalf of OpenAIRE (EU). This transfer is carried out in compliance with EU Reg. 2016/679, including Art. 45 thereof, and on the basis of the Commission Decision of 26 July 2000 pursuant to Directive 95/46/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council on the adequate protection of personal data provided in Switzerland (notified under document number C(2000) 2304).

All the documentation collected during the research may be reviewed by Committees of Italian and foreign scientific journals and international organizations to ensure that the research is conducted correctly and in accordance with applicable regulations. In any case, data transfers will respect applicable legislation, including Reg. UE 2016/679.

VIII. DATA SUBJECT RIGHTS

In their capacity as a data subject, the research participant has the right to exercise all the rights provided for in Articles 15 and following of the European Regulation. In particular, they can obtain:

- access to their personal data and all other information indicated in Article 15;
- rectification of data if they are inaccurate and/or their completion if they are incomplete;
- erasure (the so-called "right to be forgotten"), except for information that must be retained for the purposes outlined in Section IV and unless there is a prevailing legitimate reason for continuing data processing;
- restriction of processing in cases specified in Article 18;
- object to processing (in cases provided for by regulations);
- data portability (in cases provided for by regulations).

According to the provisions of the European Regulation, data subjects also have the right to:

- withdraw consent at any time without affecting the lawfulness of processing based on consent before its withdrawal;
- lodge a complaint with a supervisory authority.

IX. EXERCISE OF RIGHTS AND COMPLAINT TO THE DATA PROTECTION AUTHORITY

If the data subject wishes to exercise the rights described above, they may contact the Data Controller using the contact information provided in Section II of this notice.

For reporting any violations of personal data processing rules or to report data breaches (where a data breach refers to a security incident that results in the accidental or unlawful destruction, loss, alteration, unauthorized disclosure, or access to personal data transmitted, stored, or otherwise processed), the data subject can also use the dedicated data breach reporting service activated by the University of Siena, reachable at the following addresses: rpd.breach@pec.unisipec.it; abuse@unisi.it. The data breach reporting service operates under the authority and direct control of the Data Controller. A response to the request will be provided as soon as possible. According to the Regulation, a response should be given within one month of the request, which can be extended to three months in cases of particular complexity.

The data subject also has the right to lodge a complaint with the supervisory authority as provided in Article 77 of the Regulation. In Italy, the supervisory authority is represented by the Garante per la Protezione dei dati personali (<https://www.garanteprivacy.it>).

X. DATA RETENTION PERIOD

The data collected during the research will be recorded, processed, and stored for the duration necessary for the completion of the CIRCE project as described in Section I. Furthermore, the data may be further retained and processed in accordance with Article 89 of the EU Regulation, that is ensuring adequate safeguards to protect the rights and freedoms of the data subject, and in compliance with Article 99 of Legislative Decree 196/2003 and other regulations concerning data processing for the purposes of public interest archiving, scientific or historical research, and statistical purposes.

In particular, the management and storage of personal data collected for research purposes in Italy are carried out by the University of Siena, including any data processors appointed by the University to ensure its operation and services, and by CNR-ILC. Details of the data storage methods can be found in the *Data Management Plan*, accessible from the dedicated section of the CIRCE website (<https://www.circe-project.eu>).

XI. NATURE OF DATA PROVISION AND CONSEQUENCES OF REFUSAL TO PROVIDE

The provision of data for the purposes described in Section IV, letter a), is essential for the conduct of the study and is not a legal obligation. Refusal to provide these data will prevent the data subject from participating in the study in question.

The provision of data for the purposes described in Section IV, letters b) and c), is optional, not required by law, and is intended to facilitate the retention of data for a longer period than that envisaged for the conclusion of the present study, potentially allowing the Data Controller, through the Scientific Coordinator of the ongoing project, to contact you for the purpose of obtaining new, specific consent (should you deem it appropriate) for further research.

CONSENT FORM

Subject: Collection of pseudo-anonymised voices as part of the CIRCE Project

Legal name _____

Place of birth: _____ (_____)

Date of birth: ____/____/____

Legal address: _____

I express my consent to participate in the project in question and I hereby authorize the university staff working within the CIRCE project (researchers, research collaborators) to:

- record short samples of voices (read speech);
- carry out surveys by means of a sociolinguistic questionnaire (in paper and/or digital form);
- use the above-mentioned contents both in their entirety and partially, for the purposes of sociolinguistic research, including publications and research reports as well as quotations during lectures, seminars and conferences and statistical analyses;
- disseminate and reproduce the above-mentioned contents, both in paper and digital form in the ways that the University will deem appropriate;

I hereby declare that:

- I have been adequately informed about the aims of the project and the way in which my contribution may be used;
- I have nothing to claim from the University of Siena regarding the use of the material collected as indicated above, neither now nor in the future;
- the copyright of the data obtained through registration is the total property of the University of Siena, which owns all the rights of reproduction, publication and dissemination according to the uses permitted by law.

Date _____

Signature _____

PROCESSING OF PERSONAL DATA

You are invited to read the detailed Privacy Policy drafted according to EU Regulation 2016/679, which is delivered to you together with this form, and you are informed that:

- Your data will be processed in accordance with the principles established in Article 5 (lawfulness, correctness, transparency, appropriateness, relevance, accuracy, minimisation of processing, limitation of storage, etc.); under the terms of the related joint-controller agreement, the Data Controllers are:
 - **The Università degli Studi di Siena**, with headquarters in Banchi di Sotto 55, 53100 Siena – Italy, represented by, Prof. Dr. **, Legal Representative, Rector;
 - **The Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche**, with headquarters in Piazzale Aldo Moro 7, 00185 Roma – Italy, represented by Dr. **, Legal Representative, Director of the Istituto di Linguistica Computazionale “Antonio Zampolli” of the Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche,

with headquarters in the Area della Ricerca del CNR di Pisa, Via Giuseppe Moruzzi 1, 56124 Pisa ITALY;

- **The Universitaet Hamburg**, with headquarters in Mittelweg 177 20148 Hamburg – Germany, represented by Prof. Dr. **, Legal Representative President of Universität Hamburg;
 - **The Westfaelische Wilhelms-Universitaet Muenster**, with headquarters in Schlossplatz 2, 48149 Muenster – Germany, represented by Dr. **;
 - **The Universidade de Évora**, with headquarters in Largo dos Colegiais, 2 7000-803 Évora – Portugal, represented by Prof. Dr. **, Legal Representative, Vice-Rector.
- The Data Protection Officers (DPO) of the joint Data Controllers are:
 - **Università degli Studi di Siena**
DPO: Dr. **
Email: rpd@unisi.it
Certified Email (PEC): rpd@pec.unisipec.it
 - **Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche**
Email: rpd@cnr.it
Certified Email (PEC): rpd@pec.cnr.it
 - **Universitaet Hamburg**
DPO: **
Email: datenschutz@uni-hamburg.de
 - **Westfaelische Wilhelms-Universitaet Muenster**
DPO: **
Email: datenschutz@uni-muenster.de
 - **Universidade de Évora**
DPO: Prof. **
Email: epd@uevora.pt
 - The data will be acquired for the purposes of the University of Siena's sociolinguistic research, including publications and research reports as well as quotations during lectures, seminars and conferences, for sociolinguistic analyses; to carry out institutional communications (including interactive ones). They will be collected and processed with the aid of paper and computer instruments in such a way as to guarantee security and confidentiality, feeding paper and/or computer archives;
 - As a data subject, you may exercise against the University of Siena all the rights envisaged by Articles 15 et seq. of the European Regulation; in particular, you may obtain: access to your personal data, their rectification or integration, their deletion (so-called "right to be forgotten"), the restriction of processing.
 - Giving consent to the processing of your personal data is optional. In the absence of your consent, you will not be able to participate in the CIRCE project of which the University of Siena is the lead partner, in a partnership consisting of:
CNR - Institute of Computational Linguistics "Antonio Zampolli" (ILC, Pisa);
WESTFAELISCHE WILHELMS-UNIVERSITAET MUENSTER (UM, Germany);
UNIVERSITAET HAMBURG (UH, Germany);
UNIVERSIDADE DE EVORA (EU, Portugal);
VISOKOSKOLSKA USTANOVA INTERNACIONALNI BURC UNIVERZITET – INTERNATIONAL BURCH UNIVERSITY (IBU, Bosnia and Herzegovina).

The undersigned _____

having carefully read the information notice on the processing of their personal data

consents to the processing of their personal data for all the purposes specified in Title IV of the privacy policy

does not consent to the processing of their personal data

Date _____

Signature _____

Consent form for photos or audio-audiovideo interviews (social media)

DISCLAIMER

Location: Event:

I, the undersigned, (FULL NAME) born in
..... on/...../.....

AUTHORIZE

the personnel working on the project CIRCE COUNTERACTING ACCENT DISCRIMINATION PRACTICES IN EDUCATION (CIRCE) ID 1345220 – ERASMUS+ PROGRAMME PROJECT1 SECTOR SCHOOL EDUCATION ACTIVITY KA2 AGREEMENT NO. 2022-1-IT02-KA220-SCH-000087602, to:

- take photographs, videos, and/or audio recordings of myself on film, tape, card, or any other medium within the scope of the above-mentioned event;
- use the above-mentioned content in whole or in part;
- publish, distribute, and broadcast the above-mentioned material using any communication tool (radio, TV, internet, etc.), any form and method, and with any technical means (film, tape, digital media, etc.) present and future.

PROHIBIT

- the use of my images in contexts that may compromise personal dignity and decorum.

DECLARE

- not to expect anything from the University of Siena regarding the use of videos and audio and video material as indicated above, neither for the current year nor for the years to come;
- that the copyright of photos, video recordings, and audio recordings is the sole property of the University of Siena, which possesses all reproduction, publication, and dissemination rights as allowed by law.

The subject being photographed/recorded (clear signature)

Date Signature

PRIVACY POLICY

The privacy policy, drafted according to the indications of Article 13 of EU Regulation 2016/679, is published on the project's website at the following address: <https://www.circe-project.eu/privacy-policy/>

I, the undersigned _____

After carefully reviewing the privacy policy concerning the processing of personal data related to the undersigned:

Explicitly consent, according to EU Regulation 2016/679, to the processing of such personal data, including special categories of personal data (so-called "sensitive" data, as per Article 9 of EU Regulation 2016/679) for the specific purposes described in point IV of the attached privacy policy.

Do not consent to the processing of my personal data.

Date Signature

Privacy policy and consent form for metalinguistic interviews (teachers)

CIRCE Project PRIVACY POLICY	
Project Title	Progetto ERASMUS+ <i>Counteracting accent discrimination pRactiCes in Education (CIRCE)</i> AGREEMENT NUMBER: 2022-1-IT02-KA220-SCH-000087602
Scientific Coordinator	Prof. Silvia Calamai (Siena University, Italy) <add name for your institution>

I. GENERAL INFORMATION

You are invited to take part in a study that aims at collecting interviews concerning the perception of linguistic diversity in language teaching (Italian and English) in school and university contexts, as well as the narration of the teaching experience lived in first person or witnessed through reports by colleagues. The audio-recorded interviews will be studied for the purposes described in point IV and may be described and collected in a corpus, which may be used for research purposes and without profit and which will be deposited in online archives accessible only upon request. More specifically, the corpus of interviews and podcasts will be deposited on Zenodo (the open access archive for researchers' publications and data managed by CERN on behalf of OpenAIRE (EU)) and on ILC4CLARIN (the data centre of the CLARIN-IT infrastructure, the Italian component of the European federation of CLARIN).

The study is being conducted by personnel belonging to the Department of Philology and Literary Criticism, in collaboration with the following partners:

CNR - Institute of Computational Linguistics 'Antonio Zampolli' (ILC, Pisa);

WESTFAELISCHE WILHELMS-UNIVERSITAET MUENSTER (UM, Germany);

UNIVERSITAET HAMBURG (UH, Germany);

UNIVERSIDADE DE EVORA (EU, Portugal);

VISOKOSKOLSKA USTANOVA INTERNACIONALNI BURC UNIVERZITET-INTERNATIONAL BURCH UNIVERSITY (IBU, Bosnia and Herzegovina).

The University, as a research centre and as joint-controller, undertakes to process the data concerning you, including "special categories of data" indicated in Article 9 of EU Regulation 2016/679 (such as, for example, personal data relating to health, racial or ethnic origin, political opinions, trade union membership, biometric data) in accordance with the principles established in Article 5 (lawfulness, fairness, transparency, appropriateness, relevance, accuracy, minimisation of processing, limitation of storage, etc.).

The University invites you to read the following notice drafted in agreement with Articles 13 and 14 of the EU Regulation 2016/679 "on the protection of individuals with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data" (hereinafter "Regulation"), also known by the acronym GDPR (General Data Protection Regulation).

II. JOINT DATA CONTROLLERS

Under the terms of the related joint-controller agreement, the Data Controllers are:

Università degli Studi di Siena

with headquarters in Banchi di Sotto 55, 53100 Siena – Italy

represented by Prof. Dr. **, Legal Representative, Rector

Email: rettore@unisi.it

Certified Email (PEC): rettore@pec.unisipec.it

Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche

with headquarters in Piazzale Aldo Moro 7, 00185 Roma – Italy

represented by Dr. **, Legal Representative, Director of the Istituto di Linguistica Computazionale "Antonio Zampolli" of the Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche, with headquarters in the Area della Ricerca del CNR di Pisa, Via Giuseppe Moruzzi 1, 56124 Pisa ITALY

Email: direttore@ilc.cnr.it

Certified Email (PEC): protocollo.ilc@pec.cnr.it

Universitaet Hamburg

with headquarters in Mittelweg 177 20148 Hamburg – Germany
represented by Prof. Dr. **, Legal Representative, President of Universitaet Hamburg
Email: praesident@uni-hamburg.de

Westfaelische Wilhelms-Universitaet Muenster

with headquarters in Schlossplatz 2, 48149 Muenster – Germany
represented by Dr. **, Legal Representative
Email: **@uni-muenster.de

Universidade de Évora

with headquarters in Largo dos Colegiais, 2 7000-803 Évora – Portugal
represented by Prof. Dr. **, Legal Representative, Vice-Rector
Email: investigar@scc.uevora.pt

The essential content of the joint-controller agreement will be made available to the data subject upon their request via email at gdpr.circe@unisi.it.

III. DATA PROTECTION OFFICERS

The Data Protection Officers of the joint Data Controllers are:

Università degli Studi di Siena

DPO: Dr. **
Email: rpd@unisi.it
Certified Email (PEC): rpd@pec.unisipec.it

Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche

Email: rpd@cnr.it
Certified Email (PEC): rpd@pec.cnr.it

Universitaet Hamburg

DPO: **
Email: datenschutz@uni-hamburg.de

Westfaelische Wilhelms-Universitaet Muenster

DPO: **
Email: datenschutz@uni-muenster.de

Universidade de Évora

DPO: Prof. **
Email: epd@uevora.pt

IV. PURPOSES AND MEANS OF DATA PROCESSING

a) The processing purposes of your personal data are as follows:

- carrying out the "CIRCE" research project and achieving its objectives as described in Section I;
- dissemination of the results of the "CIRCE" project;
- administrative management of the project.

b) Your personal data, especially those belonging to special categories (Article 9 GDPR), will be collected and processed with appropriate levels of security, specifically:

- in a way that allows your identification only when strictly necessary;
- in paper or electronic form, feeding paper and/or electronic archives for research-related needs;
- exclusively within premises and systems (hardware and software) that are protected and compliant with security measures prescribed by regulations and security standards.

c) Considering that new discoveries may indicate fresh research opportunities for researchers or enable further studies and investigations on the data provided by you, your personal data may be processed for additional research purposes, in accordance with applicable regulations. Additionally, the Scientific Coordinator of the ongoing project may contact you to seek your new, specific consent (should you deem it appropriate) for further research on your data.

The categories of personal data processed include:

- oral and audio-visual data (audio and video interviews, short life stories, podcasts), which may include special categories of personal data under Article 9 of EU Regulation 2016/679;
- written linguistic autobiographies, which may include special categories of personal data;
- behavioural data, such as reaction times and responses to auditory stimuli, which may be processed for statistical analysis.

For the processing of images, specific consent from the data subject is required, in accordance with copyright law provisions.

V. LEGAL BASIS

The processing of your personal data by the University will be carried out on the basis of at least one of the following legal grounds for processing, or "lawful bases for processing":

- explicit consent provided by the data subject for one or more processing purposes as outlined in Section IV of this policy.
- pursuit of a legitimate interest, which consists in the execution and development of the CIRCE project and is therefore related to the achievement of the purposes described in Section IV of this policy.

The processing of personal data belonging to "special categories" (formerly known as "sensitive data") will be carried out on the basis of at least one of the following legal grounds for processing:

- explicit consent of the data subject for one or more of the purposes indicated in Section IV of this policy.
- necessity to establish, exercise, or defend a legal claim in a judicial proceeding.
- archiving in the public interest, for scientific or historical research, or statistical purposes.

VI. INTERNAL RECIPIENTS OF DATA

The recipients of your personal data are partners of the project which are joint-controllers and that are listed in Section II. The research units and the collaborators in research activities of each partner (researchers, technicians, and administrative staff) may access data. They will process these data, both through automated and non-automated means, exclusively to facilitate the execution of the research and all related operations and activities, including administrative tasks.

VII. ENTITIES DIFFERENT FROM THE JOINT CONTROLLERS WITH WHOM DATA MAY BE SHARED AND TRANSFER OF PERSONAL DATA TO THIRD COUNTRIES OR INTERNATIONAL ORGANIZATIONS

The collected data may be shared for the purposes outlined in Section IV, including the sharing of research activities and subsequent dissemination of results with the project partner INTERNACIONALNI BURČ UNIVERZITET-INTERNATIONAL BURCH UNIVERSITY (IBU, Bosnia and Herzegovina). The transfer to Bosnia, and thus outside the European Economic Area, will only be carried out after the adoption of standard data protection clauses approved by the European Commission through Implementing Decision (EU) 2021/914 of June 4, 2021, and following statements from the Bosnian partner ensuring the adequacy of the level of protection guaranteed by the national legislation applicable to the processing of personal data.

The collected data may also be shared, again for the purposes outlined in Section IV, with the Zenodo repository (<https://zenodo.org/>), operated by CERN (Switzerland) on behalf of OpenAIRE (EU). This transfer is carried out in compliance with EU Reg. 2016/679, including Art. 45 thereof, and on the basis of the Commission Decision of 26 July 2000 pursuant to Directive 95/46/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council on the adequate protection of personal data provided in Switzerland (notified under document number C(2000) 2304).

All the documentation collected during the research may be reviewed by Committees of Italian and foreign scientific journals and international organizations to ensure that the research is conducted correctly and in accordance with applicable regulations. In any case, data transfers will respect applicable legislation, including Reg. UE 2016/679.

VIII. DATA SUBJECT RIGHTS

In their capacity as a data subject, the research participant has the right to exercise all the rights provided for in Articles 15 and following of the European Regulation. In particular, they can obtain:

- access to their personal data and all other information indicated in Article 15;
- rectification of data if they are inaccurate and/or their completion if they are incomplete;
- erasure (the so-called "right to be forgotten"), except for information that must be retained for the purposes outlined in Section IV and unless there is a prevailing legitimate reason for continuing data processing;
- restriction of processing in cases specified in Article 18;
- object to processing (in cases provided for by regulations);
- data portability (in cases provided for by regulations).

According to the provisions of the European Regulation, data subjects also have the right to:

- withdraw consent at any time without affecting the lawfulness of processing based on consent before its withdrawal;
- lodge a complaint with a supervisory authority.

IX. EXERCISE OF RIGHTS AND COMPLAINT TO THE DATA PROTECTION AUTHORITY

If the data subject wishes to exercise the rights described above, they may contact the Data Controller using the contact information provided in Section II of this notice.

For reporting any violations of personal data processing rules or to report data breaches (where a data breach refers to a security incident that results in the accidental or unlawful destruction, loss, alteration, unauthorized disclosure, or access to personal data transmitted, stored, or otherwise processed), the data subject can also use the dedicated data breach reporting service activated by the University of Siena, reachable at the following addresses: rp.d.breach@pec.unisipec.it; abuse@unisi.it. The data breach reporting service operates under the authority and direct control of the Data Controller.

A response to the request will be provided as soon as possible. According to the Regulation, a response should be given within one month of the request, which can be extended to three months in cases of particular complexity.

The data subject also has the right to lodge a complaint with the supervisory authority as provided in Article 77 of the Regulation. In Italy, the supervisory authority is represented by the Garante per la Protezione dei dati personali (<https://www.garanteprivacy.it>).

X. DATA RETENTION PERIOD

The data collected during the research will be recorded, processed, and stored for the duration necessary for the completion of the CIRCE project as described in Section I. Furthermore, the data may be further retained and processed in accordance with Article 89 of the EU Regulation, that is ensuring adequate safeguards to protect the rights and freedoms of the data subject, and in compliance with Article 99 of Legislative Decree 196/2003 and other regulations concerning data processing for the purposes of public interest archiving, scientific or historical research, and statistical purposes.

In particular, the management and storage of personal data collected for research purposes in Italy are carried out by the University of Siena, including any data processors appointed by the University to ensure its operation and services, and by CNR-ILC. Details of the data storage methods can be found in the *Data Management Plan*, accessible from the dedicated section of the CIRCE website (<https://www.circe-project.eu>).

XI. NATURE OF DATA PROVISION AND CONSEQUENCES OF REFUSAL TO PROVIDE

The provision of data for the purposes described in Section IV, letter a), is essential for the conduct of the study and is not a legal obligation. Refusal to provide these data will prevent the data subject from participating in the study in question.

The provision of data for the purposes described in Section IV, letters b) and c), is optional, not required by law, and is intended to facilitate the retention of data for a longer period than that envisaged for the conclusion of the present study, potentially allowing the Data Controller, through the Scientific Coordinator of the ongoing project, to contact you for the purpose of obtaining new, specific consent (should you deem it appropriate) for further research.

CONSENT FORM

Subject: Collection of metalinguistic interviews as part of the CIRCE Project

Legal name _____

Place of birth: _____ (_____)

Date of birth: ____/____/____

Legal address: _____

I express my consent to participate in the project in question and I hereby authorize the university staff working within the CIRCE project (researchers, research collaborators) to:

- record an interview on the perception of linguistic diversity in teaching experiences (metalinguistic interview);

- use the interview content both in its entirety and partially, for the purposes of sociolinguistic research, including publications and research reports as well as quotations during lectures, seminars and conferences and statistical analyses;
- include the above-mentioned contents within a corpus that can be used for research and non-profit purposes, which will be deposited in online archives accessible only upon request;

I hereby declare that:

- I have been adequately informed about the aims of the project and the way in which my contribution may be used;
- I have nothing to claim from the University of Siena regarding the use of the material collected as indicated above, either now or in the future;
- the copyright of the data obtained through the interview is the total property of the University of Siena, which owns all the rights of reproduction, publication and dissemination according to the uses permitted by law.

Date _____

Signature _____

PROCESSING OF PERSONAL DATA

You are invited to read the detailed Privacy Policy drafted according to EU Regulation 2016/679, which is delivered to you together with this form, and you are informed that:

- Your data will be processed in accordance with the principles established in Article 5 (lawfulness, correctness, transparency, appropriateness, relevance, accuracy, minimisation of processing, limitation of storage, etc.); under the terms of the related joint-controller agreement, the Data Controllers are:
 - **The Università degli Studi di Siena**, with headquarters in Banchi di Sotto 55, 53100 Siena – Italy, represented by, Prof. Dr. **, Legal Representative, Rector;
 - **The Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche**, with headquarters in Piazzale Aldo Moro 7, 00185 Roma – Italy, represented by Dr. **, Legal Representative, Director of the Istituto di Linguistica Computazionale “Antonio Zampolli” of the Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche, with headquarters in the Area della Ricerca del CNR di Pisa, Via Giuseppe Moruzzi 1, 56124 Pisa ITALY;
 - **The Universitaet Hamburg**, with headquarters in Mittelweg 177 20148 Hamburg – Germany, represented by Prof. Dr. **, Legal Representative President of Universität Hamburg;
 - **The Westfaelische Wilhelms-Universitaet Muenster**, with headquarters in Schlossplatz 2, 48149 Muenster – Germany, represented by Dr. **;
 - **The Universidade de Évora**, with headquarters in Largo dos Colegiais, 2 7000-803 Évora – Portugal, represented by Prof. Dr. **, Legal Representative, Vice-Rector.
- The Data Protection Officers (DPO) of the joint Data Controllers are:
 - **Università degli Studi di Siena**
DPO: Dr. **
Email: rpd@unisi.it
Certified Email (PEC): rpd@pec.unisipec.it
 - **Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche**

Email: rpd@cnr.it

Certified Email (PEC): rpd@pec.cnr.it

○ **Universitaet Hamburg**

DPO: **

Email: datenschutz@uni-hamburg.de

○ **Westfaelische Wilhelms-Universitaet Muenster**

DPO: **

Email: datenschutz@uni-muenster.de

○ **Universidade de Évora**

DPO: Prof. **

Email: epd@uevora.pt

- The data will be acquired for the purposes of the University of Siena's sociolinguistic research, including publications and research reports as well as quotations during lectures, seminars and conferences, for sociolinguistic analyses; to carry out institutional communications (including interactive ones). They will be collected and processed with the aid of paper and computer instruments in such a way as to guarantee security and confidentiality, feeding paper and/or computer archives;
- As a data subject, you may exercise against the University of Siena all the rights envisaged by Articles 15 et seq. of the European Regulation; in particular, you may obtain: access to your personal data, their rectification or integration, their deletion (so-called "right to be forgotten"), the restriction of processing.
- Giving consent to the processing of your personal data is optional. In the absence of your consent, you will not be able to participate in the CIRCE project of which the University of Siena is the lead partner, in a partnership consisting of:
CNR - Institute of Computational Linguistics "Antonio Zampolli" (ILC, Pisa);
WESTFAELISCHE WILHELMS-UNIVERSITAET MUENSTER (UM, Germany);
UNIVERSITAET HAMBURG (UH, Germany);
UNIVERSIDADE DE EVORA (EU, Portugal);
VISOKOSKOLSKA USTANOVA INTERNACIONALNI BURC UNIVERZITET – INTERNATIONAL BURCH UNIVERSITY (IBU, Bosnia and Herzegovina).

The undersigned _____

having carefully read the information notice on the processing of their personal data

consents to the processing of their personal data for all the purposes specified in Title IV of the privacy policy

does not consent to the processing of their personal data

Date _____

Signature _____

Privacy policy and consent form for metalinguistic interviews (students)

CIRCE Project PRIVACY POLICY

Project Title	Progetto ERASMUS+ <i>Counteracting accent discrimination pRactiCes in Education (CIRCE)</i> AGREEMENT NUMBER: 2022-1-IT02-KA220-SCH-000087602
Scientific Coordinator	Prof. Silvia Calamai (Siena University, Italy) <add name for your institution>

I. GENERAL INFORMATION

You are invited to take part in a study that aims at collecting interviews concerning the perception of linguistic diversity in language teaching (Italian and English) in school and university contexts, as well as the account of any experience of language discrimination experienced first-hand or witnessed through accounts of friends.

The audio-recorded interviews will be studied for the purposes described in point IV and may be described and collected in a corpus, which may be used for research purposes and without profit and which will be deposited in online archives accessible only upon request. More specifically, the corpus of interviews and the podcasts will be deposited on Zenodo (the open access archive for researchers' publications and data managed by CERN on behalf of OpenAIRE (EU)) and on ILC4CLARIN (the data centre of the CLARIN-IT infrastructure, the Italian component of the European federation of CLARIN).

The study is being conducted by personnel belonging to the Department of Philology and Literary Criticism, in collaboration with the following partners:

CNR - Institute of Computational Linguistics 'Antonio Zampolli' (ILC, Pisa);

WESTFAELISCHE WILHELMS-UNIVERSITAET MUENSTER (UM, Germany);

UNIVERSITAET HAMBURG (UH, Germany);

UNIVERSIDADE DE EVORA (EU, Portugal);

VISOKOSKOLSKA USTANOVA INTERNACIONALNI BURC UNIVERZITET-INTERNATIONAL BURCH UNIVERSITY (IBU, Bosnia and Herzegovina).

The University, as a research centre and as joint-controller, undertakes to process the data concerning you, including "special categories of data" indicated in Article 9 of EU Regulation 2016/679 (such as, for example, personal data relating to health, racial or ethnic origin, political opinions, trade union membership, biometric data) in accordance with the principles established in Article 5 (lawfulness, fairness, transparency, appropriateness, relevance, accuracy, minimisation of processing, limitation of storage, etc.).

The University invites you to read the following notice drafted in agreement with Articles 13 and 14 of the EU Regulation 2016/679 "on the protection of individuals with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data" (hereinafter "Regulation"), also known by the acronym GDPR (General Data Protection Regulation).

II. JOINT DATA CONTROLLERS

Under the terms of the related joint-controller agreement, the Data Controllers are:

Università degli Studi di Siena

with headquarters in Banchi di Sotto 55, 53100 Siena – Italy

represented by Prof. Dr. **, Legal Representative, Rector

Email: rettore@unisi.it Certified Email (PEC): rettore@pec.unisipec.it

Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche

with headquarters in Piazzale Aldo Moro 7, 00185 Roma – Italy
represented by Dr. **, Legal Representative, Director of the Istituto di Linguistica Computazionale “Antonio Zampolli” of the Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche, with headquarters in the Area della Ricerca del CNR di Pisa, Via Giuseppe Moruzzi 1, 56124 Pisa ITALY
Email: direttore@ilc.cnr.it Certified Email (PEC): protocollo.ilc@pec.cnr.it

Universitaet Hamburg

with headquarters in Mittelweg 177 20148 Hamburg – Germany
represented by Prof. Dr. **, Legal Representative, President of Universitaet Hamburg
Email: praesident@uni-hamburg.de

Westfaelische Wilhelms-Universitaet Muenster

with headquarters in Schlossplatz 2, 48149 Muenster – Germany
represented by Dr. **, Legal Representative
Email: katharina.steinberg@uni-muenster.de

Universidade de Évora

with headquarters in Largo dos Colegiais, 2 7000-803 Évora – Portugal
represented by Prof. Dr. **, Legal Representative, Vice-Rector
Email: investigar@scc.uevora.pt

The essential content of the joint-controller agreement will be made available to the data subject upon their request via email at gdpr.circe@unisi.it.

III. DATA PROTECTION OFFICERS

The Data Protection Officers of the joint Data Controllers are:

Università degli Studi di Siena

DPO: Dr. **
Email: rpd@unisi.it
Certified Email (PEC): rpd@pec.unisipec.it

Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche

Email: rpd@cnr.it
Certified Email (PEC): rpd@pec.cnr.it

Universitaet Hamburg

DPO: **
Email: datenschutz@uni-hamburg.de

Westfaelische Wilhelms-Universitaet Muenster

DPO: **
Email: datenschutz@uni-muenster.de

Universidade de Évora

DPO: Prof. **
Email: epd@uevora.pt

IV. PURPOSES AND MEANS OF DATA PROCESSING

a) The processing purposes of your personal data are as follows:

- carrying out the "CIRCE" research project and achieving its objectives as described in Section I;
- dissemination of the results of the "CIRCE" project;
- administrative management of the project.

b) Your personal data, especially those belonging to special categories (Article 9 GDPR), will be collected and processed with appropriate levels of security, specifically:

- in a way that allows your identification only when strictly necessary;
- in paper or electronic form, feeding paper and/or electronic archives for research-related needs;
- exclusively within premises and systems (hardware and software) that are protected and compliant with security measures prescribed by regulations and security standards.

c) Considering that new discoveries may indicate fresh research opportunities for researchers or enable further studies and investigations on the data provided by you, your personal data may be processed for additional research purposes, in accordance with applicable regulations. Additionally, the Scientific Coordinator of the ongoing project may contact you to seek your new, specific consent (should you deem it appropriate) for further research on your data.

V. LEGAL BASIS

The processing of your personal data by the University will be carried out on the basis of at least one of the following legal grounds for processing, or "lawful bases for processing":

- explicit consent provided by the data subject for one or more processing purposes as outlined in Section IV of this policy.
- pursuit of a legitimate interest, which consists in the execution and development of the CIRCE project and is therefore related to the achievement of the purposes described in Section IV of this policy.

The processing of personal data belonging to "special categories" (formerly known as "sensitive data") will be carried out on the basis of at least one of the following legal grounds for processing:

- explicit consent of the data subject for one or more of the purposes indicated in Section IV of this policy.
- necessity to establish, exercise, or defend a legal claim in a judicial proceeding.
- archiving in the public interest, for scientific or historical research, or statistical purposes.

VI. INTERNAL RECIPIENTS OF DATA

The recipients of your personal data are partners of the project which are joint-controllers and that are listed in Section II. The research units and the collaborators in research activities of each partner (researchers, technicians, and administrative staff) may access data. They will process these data, both through automated and non-automated means, exclusively to facilitate the execution of the research and all related operations and activities, including administrative tasks.

VII. ENTITIES DIFFERENT FROM THE JOINT CONTROLLERS WITH WHOM DATA MAY BE SHARED AND TRANSFER OF PERSONAL DATA TO THIRD COUNTRIES OR INTERNATIONAL ORGANIZATIONS

The collected data may be shared for the purposes outlined in Section IV, including the sharing of research activities and subsequent dissemination of results with the project partner INTERNACIONALNI BURČ UNIVERZITET-INTERNATIONAL BURCH UNIVERSITY (IBU, Bosnia and Herzegovina). The transfer to Bosnia, and thus outside the European Economic Area, will only be carried out after the adoption of standard data

protection clauses approved by the European Commission through Implementing Decision (EU) 2021/914 of June 4, 2021, and following statements from the Bosnian partner ensuring the adequacy of the level of protection guaranteed by the national legislation applicable to the processing of personal data.

The collected data may also be shared, again for the purposes outlined in Section IV, with the Zenodo repository (<https://zenodo.org/>), operated by CERN (Switzerland) on behalf of OpenAIRE (EU). This transfer is carried out in compliance with EU Reg. 2016/679, including Art. 45 thereof, and on the basis of the Commission Decision of 26 July 2000 pursuant to Directive 95/46/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council on the adequate protection of personal data provided in Switzerland (notified under document number C(2000) 2304).

All the documentation collected during the research may be reviewed by Committees of Italian and foreign scientific journals and international organizations to ensure that the research is conducted correctly and in accordance with applicable regulations. In any case, data transfers will respect applicable legislation, including Reg. UE 2016/679.

VIII. DATA SUBJECT RIGHTS

In their capacity as a data subject, the research participant has the right to exercise all the rights provided for in Articles 15 and following of the European Regulation. In particular, they can obtain:

- access to their personal data and all other information indicated in Article 15;
- rectification of data if they are inaccurate and/or their completion if they are incomplete;
- erasure (the so-called "right to be forgotten"), except for information that must be retained for the purposes outlined in Section IV and unless there is a prevailing legitimate reason for continuing data processing;
- restriction of processing in cases specified in Article 18;
- object to processing (in cases provided for by regulations);
- data portability (in cases provided for by regulations).

According to the provisions of the European Regulation, data subjects also have the right to:

- withdraw consent at any time without affecting the lawfulness of processing based on consent before its withdrawal;
- lodge a complaint with a supervisory authority.

IX. EXERCISE OF RIGHTS AND COMPLAINT TO THE DATA PROTECTION AUTHORITY

If the data subject wishes to exercise the rights described above, they may contact the Data Controller using the contact information provided in Section II of this notice.

For reporting any violations of personal data processing rules or to report data breaches (where a data breach refers to a security incident that results in the accidental or unlawful destruction, loss, alteration, unauthorized disclosure, or access to personal data transmitted, stored, or otherwise processed), the data subject can also use the dedicated data breach reporting service activated by the University of Siena, reachable at the following addresses: rpd.breach@pec.unisipec.it; abuse@unisi.it. The data breach reporting service operates under the authority and direct control of the Data Controller. A response to the request will be provided as soon as possible. According to the Regulation, a response should be given within one month of the request, which can be extended to three months in cases of particular complexity.

The data subject also has the right to lodge a complaint with the supervisory authority as provided in Article 77 of the Regulation. In Italy, the supervisory authority is represented by the Garante per la Protezione dei dati personali (<https://www.garanteprivacy.it>).

X. DATA RETENTION PERIOD

The data collected during the research will be recorded, processed, and stored for the duration necessary for the completion of the CIRCE project as described in Section I. Furthermore, the data may be further retained and processed in accordance with Article 89 of the EU Regulation, that is ensuring adequate safeguards to protect the rights and freedoms of the data subject, and in compliance with Article 99 of Legislative Decree 196/2003 and other regulations concerning data processing for the purposes of public interest archiving, scientific or historical research, and statistical purposes.

In particular, the management and storage of personal data collected for research purposes in Italy are carried out by the University of Siena, including any data processors appointed by the University to ensure its operation and services, and by CNR-ILC. Details of the data storage methods can be found in the *Data Management Plan*, accessible from the dedicated section of the CIRCE website (<https://www.circe-project.eu>).

XI. NATURE OF DATA PROVISION AND CONSEQUENCES OF REFUSAL TO PROVIDE

The provision of data for the purposes described in Section IV, letter a), is essential for the conduct of the study and is not a legal obligation. Refusal to provide these data will prevent the data subject from participating in the study in question.

The provision of data for the purposes described in Section IV, letters b) and c), is optional, not required by law, and is intended to facilitate the retention of data for a longer period than that envisaged for the conclusion of the present study, potentially allowing the Data Controller, through the Scientific Coordinator of the ongoing project, to contact you for the purpose of obtaining new, specific consent (should you deem it appropriate) for further research.

CONSENT FORM

Subject: Collection of metalinguistic interviews as part of the CIRCE Project

- The interviewee is a minor

Parent/Guardian legal name: _____

Place of birth: _____ (_____)

Date of birth: ____/____/____

Legal address: _____

Interviewee legal name: _____

- The interviewee is an adult

Interviewee legal name: _____

Place of birth: _____ (_____)

Date of birth: ____/____/____

Legal address: _____

I express my consent to participate in the project in question and I hereby authorize the university staff working within the CIRCE project (researchers, research collaborators) to:

- record an interview on the perception of linguistic diversity in teaching experiences (metalinguistic interview);
- use the interview content both in its entirety and partially, for the purposes of sociolinguistic research, including publications and research reports as well as quotations during lectures, seminars and conferences and statistical analyses;
- include the above-mentioned contents within a corpus that can be used for research and non-profit purposes, which will be deposited in online archives accessible only upon request;

I hereby declare that:

- I have been adequately informed about the aims of the project and the way in which my/my son's/my daughter's/my ward's contribution may be used;
- I have nothing to claim from the University of Siena regarding the use of the material collected as indicated above, either now or in the future;
- the copyright of the data obtained through the interview is the total property of the University of Siena, which owns all the rights of reproduction, publication and dissemination according to the uses permitted by law.

Date _____

Signature _____

PROCESSING OF PERSONAL DATA

You are invited to read the detailed Privacy Policy drafted according to EU Regulation 2016/679, which is delivered to you together with this form, and you are informed that:

- Your/your son's/your daughter's/your ward's data will be processed in accordance with the principles established in Article 5 (lawfulness, correctness, transparency, appropriateness, relevance, accuracy, minimisation of processing, limitation of storage, etc.); under the terms of the related joint-controller agreement, the Data Controllers are:
 - **The Università degli Studi di Siena**, with headquarters in Banchi di Sotto 55, 53100 Siena – Italy, represented by, Prof. Dr. **, Legal Representative, Rector;
 - **The Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche**, with headquarters in Piazzale Aldo Moro 7, 00185 Roma – Italy, represented by Dr. **, Legal Representative, Director of the Istituto di Linguistica Computazionale “Antonio Zampolli” of the Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche, with headquarters in the Area della Ricerca del CNR di Pisa, Via Giuseppe Moruzzi 1, 56124 Pisa ITALY;
 - **The Universitaet Hamburg**, with headquarters in Mittelweg 177 20148 Hamburg – Germany, represented by Prof. Dr. **, Legal Representative President of Universität Hamburg;
 - **The Westfaelische Wilhelms-Universitaet Muenster**, with headquarters in Schlossplatz 2, 48149 Muenster – Germany, represented by Dr. **;
 - **The Universidade de Évora**, with headquarters in Largo dos Colegiais, 2 7000-803 Évora – Portugal, represented by Prof. Dr. **, Legal Representative, Vice-Rector.
- The Data Protection Officers (DPO) of the joint Data Controllers are:
 - **Università degli Studi di Siena**
DPO: Dr. **
Email: rpd@unisi.it
Certified Email (PEC): rpd@pec.unisipec.it

- **Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche**
Email: rpd@cnr.it
Certified Email (PEC): rpd@pec.cnr.it
- **Universitaet Hamburg**
DPO: **
Email: datenschutz@uni-hamburg.de
- **Westfaelische Wilhelms-Universitaet Muenster**
DPO: **
Email: datenschutz@uni-muenster.de
- **Universidade de Évora**
DPO: **
Email: epd@uevora.pt

- The data will be acquired for the purposes of the University of Siena's sociolinguistic research, including publications and research reports as well as quotations during lectures, seminars and conferences, for sociolinguistic analyses; to carry out institutional communications (including interactive ones). They will be collected and processed with the aid of paper and computer instruments in such a way as to guarantee security and confidentiality, feeding paper and/or computer archives;
- As a data subject, you may exercise against the University of Siena all the rights envisaged by Articles 15 et seq. of the European Regulation; in particular, you may obtain: access to your/your son's/your daughter's/your ward's personal data, their rectification or integration, their deletion (so-called "right to be forgotten"), the restriction of processing.
- Giving consent to the processing of your personal data is optional. In the absence of your consent, you will not be able to participate in the CIRCE project of which the University of Siena is the lead partner, in a partnership consisting of:
CNR - Institute of Computational Linguistics "Antonio Zampolli" (ILC, Pisa);
WESTFAELISCHE WILHELMS-UNIVERSITAET MUENSTER (UM, Germany);
UNIVERSITAET HAMBURG (UH, Germany);
UNIVERSIDADE DE EVORA (EU, Portugal);
VISOKOSKOLSKA USTANOVA INTERNACIONALNI BURC UNIVERZITET – INTERNATIONAL BURCH UNIVERSITY (IBU, Bosnia and Herzegovina).

The undersigned _____

having carefully read the information notice on the processing of their/their son's/their daughter's/their ward's personal data

consents to the processing of their/their son's/their daughter's/their ward's personal data for all the purposes specified in Title IV of the privacy policy

does not consent to the processing of their/their son's/their daughter's/their ward's personal data

Date _____

Signature _____

Privacy policy and consent form for Linguistic autobiography

CIRCE Project PRIVACY POLICY

Project Title	Progetto ERASMUS+ <i>Counteracting accent discrimination practices in Education (CIRCE)</i> AGREEMENT NUMBER: 2022-1-IT02-KA220-SCH-000087602
Scientific Coordinator	Prof. Silvia Calamai (Siena University, Italy) <add name for your institution>

I. GENERAL INFORMATION

You are invited to take part in a study that aims at collecting written linguistic autobiographies (i.e., personal reflections on the role of languages in shaping one's identity).

The written linguistic autobiographies will be studied for the purposes described in point IV and may be described and collected in a corpus, which may be used for research purposes and without profit and which will be deposited in online archives accessible only upon request. More specifically, the corpus of written linguistic autobiographies will be deposited on Zenodo (the open access archive for researchers' publications and data managed by CERN on behalf of OpenAIRE (EU)) and on ILC4CLARIN (the data centre of the CLARIN-IT infrastructure, the Italian component of the European federation of CLARIN).

The study is being conducted by personnel belonging to the Department of Philology and Literary Criticism, in collaboration with the following partners:

CNR - Institute of Computational Linguistics 'Antonio Zampolli' (ILC, Pisa);

WESTFAELISCHE WILHELMS-UNIVERSITAET MUESTER (UM, Germany);

UNIVERSITAET HAMBURG (UH, Germany);

UNIVERSIDADE DE EVORA (EU, Portugal);

VISOKOSKOLSKA USTANOVA INTERNACIONALNI BURC UNIVERZITET-INTERNACIONAL BURCH UNIVERSITY (IBU, Bosnia and Herzegovina).

The University, as a research centre and as joint-controller, undertakes to process the data concerning you, including "special categories of data" indicated in Article 9 of EU Regulation 2016/679 (such as, for example, personal data relating to health, racial or ethnic origin, political

opinions, trade union membership, biometric data) in accordance with the principles established in Article 5 (lawfulness, fairness, transparency, appropriateness, relevance, accuracy, minimisation of processing, limitation of storage, etc.).

The University invites you to read the following notice drafted in agreement with Articles 13 and 14 of the EU Regulation 2016/679 "on the protection of individuals with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data" (hereinafter "Regulation"), also known by the acronym GDPR (General Data Protection Regulation).

II. JOINT DATA CONTROLLERS

Under the terms of the related joint-controller agreement, the Data Controllers are:

Università degli Studi di Siena

with headquarters in Banchi di Sotto 55, 53100 Siena – Italy

represented by Prof. Dr. **, Legal Representative, Rector

Email: rettore@unisi.it Certified Email (PEC): rettore@pec.unisipec.it

Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche

with headquarters in Piazzale Aldo Moro 7, 00185 Roma – Italy

represented by Dr. **, Legal Representative, Director of the Istituto di Linguistica Computazionale "Antonio Zampolli" of the Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche, with headquarters in the Area della Ricerca del CNR di Pisa, Via Giuseppe Moruzzi 1, 56124 Pisa ITALY

Email: direttore@ilc.cnr.it Certified Email (PEC): protocollo.ilc@pec.cnr.it

Universitaet Hamburg

with headquarters in Mittelweg 177 20148
Hamburg – Germany
represented by Prof. Dr. **, Legal Representative,
President of Universitaet Hamburg
Email: praesident@uni-hamburg.de

Westfaelische Wilhelms-Universitaet Muenster

with headquarters in Schlossplatz 2, 48149
Muenster – Germany
represented by Dr. **, Legal Representative
Email: **@uni-muenster.de

Universidade de Évora

with headquarters in Largo dos Colegiais, 2 7000-
803 Évora – Portugal
represented by Prof. Dr. **, Legal Representative,
Vice-Rector
Email: investigar@scc.uevora.pt

The essential content of the joint-controller
agreement will be made available to the data
subject upon their request via email at
gdpr.circe@unisi.it.

III. DATA PROTECTION OFFICERS

The Data Protection Officers of the joint Data
Controllers are:

Università degli Studi di Siena

DPO: Dr. **
Email: rpd@unisi.it
Certified Email (PEC): rpd@pec.unisipec.it

Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche

Email: rpd@cnr.it
Certified Email (PEC): rpd@pec.cnr.it

Universitaet Hamburg

DPO: **
Email: datenschutz@uni-hamburg.de

Westfaelische Wilhelms-Universitaet Muenster

DPO: **
Email: datenschutz@uni-muenster.de

Universidade de Évora

DPO: **
Email: epd@uevora.pt

IV. PURPOSES AND MEANS OF DATA PROCESSING

a) The processing purposes of your personal data
are as follows:

- carrying out the "CIRCE" research project
and achieving its objectives as described
in Section I;
- dissemination of the results of the "CIRCE"
project;
- administrative management of the
project.

b) Your personal data, especially those belonging
to special categories (Article 9 GDPR), will be
collected and processed with appropriate levels of
security, specifically:

- in a way that allows your identification
only when strictly necessary;
- in paper or electronic form, feeding paper
and/or electronic archives for research-
related needs;
- exclusively within premises and systems
(hardware and software) that are
protected and compliant with security
measures prescribed by regulations and
security standards.

c) Considering that new discoveries may indicate
fresh research opportunities for researchers or
enable further studies and investigations on the
data provided by you, your personal data may be
processed for additional research purposes, in
accordance with applicable regulations.
Additionally, the Scientific Coordinator of the
ongoing project may contact you to seek your
new, specific consent (should you deem it
appropriate) for further research on your data.

V. LEGAL BASIS

The processing of your personal data by the
University will be carried out on the basis of at
least one of the following legal grounds for
processing, or "lawful bases for processing":

- explicit consent provided by the data
subject for one or more processing
purposes as outlined in Section IV of this
policy.

- pursuit of a legitimate interest, which consists in the execution and development of the CIRCE project and is therefore related to the achievement of the purposes described in Section IV of this policy.

The processing of personal data belonging to "special categories" (formerly known as "sensitive data") will be carried out on the basis of at least one of the following legal grounds for processing:

- explicit consent of the data subject for one or more of the purposes indicated in Section IV of this policy.
- necessity to establish, exercise, or defend a legal claim in a judicial proceeding.
- archiving in the public interest, for scientific or historical research, or statistical purposes.

VI. INTERNAL RECIPIENTS OF DATA

The recipients of your personal data are partners of the project which are joint-controllers and that are listed in Section II. The research units and the collaborators in research activities of each partner (researchers, technicians, and administrative staff) may access data. They will process these data, both through automated and non-automated means, exclusively to facilitate the execution of the research and all related operations and activities, including administrative tasks.

VII. ENTITIES DIFFERENT FROM THE JOINT CONTROLLERS WITH WHOM DATA MAY BE SHARED AND TRANSFER OF PERSONAL DATA TO THIRD COUNTRIES OR INTERNATIONAL ORGANIZATIONS

The collected data may be shared for the purposes outlined in Section IV, including the sharing of research activities and subsequent dissemination of results with the project partner INTERNACIONALNI BURC UNIVERZITET-INTERNATIONAL BURCH UNIVERSITY (IBU, Bosnia and Herzegovina). The transfer to Bosnia, and thus outside the European Economic Area, will only be carried out after the adoption of standard data protection clauses approved by the European Commission through Implementing Decision (EU)

2021/914 of June 4, 2021, and following statements from the Bosnian partner ensuring the adequacy of the level of protection guaranteed by the national legislation applicable to the processing of personal data.

The collected data may also be shared, again for the purposes outlined in Section IV, with the Zenodo repository (<https://zenodo.org/>), operated by CERN (Switzerland) on behalf of OpenAIRE (EU). This transfer is carried out in compliance with EU Reg. 2016/679, including Art. 45 thereof, and on the basis of the Commission Decision of 26 July 2000 pursuant to Directive 95/46/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council on the adequate protection of personal data provided in Switzerland (notified under document number C(2000) 2304).

All the documentation collected during the research may be reviewed by Committees of Italian and foreign scientific journals and international organizations to ensure that the research is conducted correctly and in accordance with applicable regulations. In any case, data transfers will respect applicable legislation, including Reg. UE 2016/679.

VIII. DATA SUBJECT RIGHTS

In their capacity as a data subject, the research participant has the right to exercise all the rights provided for in Articles 15 and following of the European Regulation. In particular, they can obtain:

- access to their personal data and all other information indicated in Article 15;
- rectification of data if they are inaccurate and/or their completion if they are incomplete;
- erasure (the so-called "right to be forgotten"), except for information that must be retained for the purposes outlined in Section IV and unless there is a prevailing legitimate reason for continuing data processing;
- restriction of processing in cases specified in Article 18;
- object to processing (in cases provided for by regulations);

- data portability (in cases provided for by regulations).

According to the provisions of the European Regulation, data subjects also have the right to:

- withdraw consent at any time without affecting the lawfulness of processing based on consent before its withdrawal;
- lodge a complaint with a supervisory authority.

IX. EXERCISE OF RIGHTS AND COMPLAINT TO THE DATA PROTECTION AUTHORITY

If the data subject wishes to exercise the rights described above, they may contact the Data Controller using the contact information provided in Section II of this notice.

For reporting any violations of personal data processing rules or to report data breaches (where a data breach refers to a security incident that results in the accidental or unlawful destruction, loss, alteration, unauthorized disclosure, or access to personal data transmitted, stored, or otherwise processed), the data subject can also use the dedicated data breach reporting service activated by the University of Siena, reachable at the following addresses: rpd.breach@pec.unisipec.it; abuse@unisi.it. The data breach reporting service operates under the authority and direct control of the Data Controller. A response to the request will be provided as soon as possible. According to the Regulation, a response should be given within one month of the request, which can be extended to three months in cases of particular complexity.

The data subject also has the right to lodge a complaint with the supervisory authority as provided in Article 77 of the Regulation. In Italy, the supervisory authority is represented by the Garante per la Protezione dei dati personali (<https://www.garanteprivacy.it>).

X. DATA RETENTION PERIOD

The data collected during the research will be recorded, processed, and stored for the duration necessary for the completion of the CIRCE project as described in Section I. Furthermore, the data may be further retained and processed in

accordance with Article 89 of the EU Regulation, that is ensuring adequate safeguards to protect the rights and freedoms of the data subject, and in compliance with Article 99 of Legislative Decree 196/2003 and other regulations concerning data processing for the purposes of public interest archiving, scientific or historical research, and statistical purposes.

In particular, the management and storage of personal data collected for research purposes in Italy are carried out by the University of Siena, including any data processors appointed by the University to ensure its operation and services, and by CNR-ILC. Details of the data storage methods can be found in the *Data Management Plan*, accessible from the dedicated section of the CIRCE website (<https://www.circe-project.eu>).

XI. NATURE OF DATA PROVISION AND CONSEQUENCES OF REFUSAL TO PROVIDE

The provision of data for the purposes described in Section IV, letter a), is essential for the conduct of the study and is not a legal obligation. Refusal to provide these data will prevent the data subject from participating in the study in question.

The provision of data for the purposes described in Section IV, letters b) and c), is optional, not required by law, and is intended to facilitate the retention of data for a longer period than that envisaged for the conclusion of the present study, potentially allowing the Data Controller, through the Scientific Coordinator of the ongoing project, to contact you for the purpose of obtaining new, specific consent (should you deem it appropriate) for further research

CONSENT FORM

Subject: Collection of written linguistic autobiographies as part of the CIRCE Project

- The subject is a minor

Parent/Guardian legal name: _____

Place of birth: _____ (_____)

Date of birth: ____/____/____

Legal address: _____

Subject legal name: _____

- The subject is an adult

Subject legal name: _____

Place of birth: _____ (_____)

Date of birth: ____/____/____

Legal address: _____

I express my consent to participate in the project in question and I hereby authorize the university staff working within the CIRCE project (researchers, research collaborators) to:

- Collect my linguistic autobiography;
- Use my linguistic autobiography both in its entirety and partially, for the purposes of sociolinguistic research, including publications and research reports as well as quotations during lectures, seminars and conferences and statistical analyses;
- include the above-mentioned contents within a corpus that can be used for research and non-profit purposes, which will be deposited in online archives accessible only upon request;

I hereby declare that:

- I have been adequately informed about the aims of the project and the way in which my/my son's/my daughter's/my ward's contribution may be used;
- I have nothing to claim from the University of Siena regarding the use of the material collected as indicated above, either now or in the future;
- the copyright of the data obtained through the linguistic autobiography is the total property of the University of Siena, which owns all the rights of reproduction, publication and dissemination according to the uses permitted by law.

Date _____

Signature _____

PROCESSING OF PERSONAL DATA

The undersigned _____

having carefully read the information notice on the processing of their/their son's/their daughter's/their ward's personal data

consents to the processing of their/their son's/their daughter's/their ward's personal data for all the purposes specified in Title IV of the privacy policy

does not consent to the processing of their/their son's/their daughter's/their ward's personal data

Date_____

Signature_____